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FACULTY OF ART HISTORY AND THEORY
MAJOR: ART HISTORY AND THEORY

BACHELOR'S THESIS

THESIS TITLE: JEAN VĂLEANU – RECOVERING THE MEMORY OF A SIGNIFICANT
CONTRIBUTOR TO THE ARCHITECTURAL LANDSCAPE OF THE CAPITAL

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Abstract

This monograph presents a comprehensive study of the architectural and artistic work of Jean Văleanu (1904–1994), emphasizing his contribution to the Art Deco heritage of Bucharest during the interwar and early postwar periods. Through systematic archival research—including municipal archives, libraries, photographic collections, and period newspapers—over thirty residential and leisure buildings were identified and analyzed, revealing Văleanu’s versatility in responding to complex urban parcels, stylistic regulations, and emerging technologies of the 1930s. His architectural oeuvre demonstrates a nuanced engagement with mature Art Deco, Streamline, and International Style tendencies, while integrating functional innovations such as optimized ventilation, lighting, and thermal comfort. Parallel to his architectural career, Văleanu pursued a lifelong practice in the visual arts, evolving from figurative landscapes and still lifes to abstract series—Masks and Structures—produced primarily in Paris from the 1980s onward. The study highlights the interplay between Văleanu’s architecture and plastic art, as well as the collaborative influence of his wife, Stela Văleanu, in glass and enamel works. Contextualized within socio-political constraints, including antisemitism and emigration, this research reconstructs Văleanu’s professional trajectory and underscores his dual legacy in Romanian architecture and fine arts. The monograph contributes to the historiography of Bucharest’s built environment, Art Deco architecture, and the recognition of overlooked creative figures in national cultural memory.

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INTRODUCTION

The 20th century in Romania's history was one of major transformations, but also of turbulence. It encompassed architectural innovations—the most prominent being the national style, traditionally labeled as “Neo-Romanian,” and the modernist style in the capital's architecture—a period of creative effervescence marked by a range of significant artistic figures. All these developments unfolded simultaneously and often intersected against the backdrop of world wars and the succession of authoritarian regimes that shaped both Romania's fate and individual destinies.

This study aims to shed light on the contribution of the Romanian architect of Jewish origin, Jean Văleanu—an architect, entrepreneur, and artist with a substantial impact on the built environment of the capital. His work remains little known, both in specialized literature and among the residents who continue to inhabit the more than 60 buildings he designed and constructed in the city.

The architect and artist Jean Văleanu has been mentioned only marginally in architectural dictionaries, with the notable exception of Vasile Țelea's Dictionary¹. He is almost entirely absent from artist dictionaries, with one exception—Vasile Florea², absent from Petre Oprea's research on group exhibitions in Romania during the period 1920–1973³ and from Ionel Jianu's work on Romanian artists in the diaspora⁴. Jean Văleanu is mentioned in only one instance in a study on the history of modernist architecture in Bucharest, as the designer of the Casata

¹ Vasile Țelea, *Personalități ale arhitecturii românești 1880-2010*, volume 2 L-Z, Rentrop & Straton Publishing house, Bucharest, 2023, p 412

² Vasile Florea, “Văleanu Jean” in *Enciclopedia artiștilor români contemporani*, volume 5, Arc 2000 publishing house, Bucharest, 2000, pagina 197

³ Petre Oprea, *Cronici plastice și texte pentru cataloage de expoziții*, publisher Maiko, Bucharest, 2010; Petre Oprea, *Două veacuri de pictură la Bucharest*, publisher Maiko, Bucharest, 2007; Petre Oprea, *Critici de artă în presa bucureșteană a anilor 1931-1937*, Editura Tehnică Agricolă, Bucharest. 1997; Petre Oprea, *Critici și cronicari de artă în presa bucureșteană a anilor 1938-1944*, publisher Maiko, Bucharest, 2007.

⁴ Ionel Jianu et al, *Les artistes Roumains en Occident*, American Romanian Academy of Arts Sciences publishing house, 1986

apartment building, which was destroyed in the earthquake of 1977⁵. Therefore, the aim of this study is not only to bring Jean Văleanu's work to light but also to correlate the historical, political, and legislative context with his marginalization, in order to explore the reasons why he has remained unacknowledged in the specialized literature.

As sources, this study drew upon primary materials: period documents from the National Archives of Romania, the Bucharest City Hall Archives, the holdings at the Kandinsky Library of the George Pompidou Museum in Paris concerning the Văleanu couple, the architect's file from the Romanian Union of Architects' archives, and the photographic archives of the National Library, the Library of the Romanian Academy, the Central University Library of Cluj-Napoca, and the Bucharest Municipal Museum. These data were supplemented with information from contemporary press articles, through which I was able to identify over 30 buildings designed by architect Jean Văleanu during the period 1932–1950. The section of the thesis dedicated to analyzing the architect's activity aims to describe his stylistic choices, the visual identity of his buildings, and the ways in which they actively contributed to shaping the urban landscape and urban development of the capital in that era. The buildings were identified with the help of period newspapers, by cataloging apartment sale advertisements from the classified sections, as well as public transactions in which the architect was involved (extracted with the aid of the Arcanum Newspapers resource⁶). For buildings that no longer exist today—whether due to earthquakes, the Allied bombings of 1944, or later demolitions—period photographs of some of these structures were obtained from available digital resources, as well as from the archives, photographic collections, and special holdings of the National Library, the Library of the Romanian Academy, the Bucharest Municipal Museum, and the Central University Library of Cluj-Napoca.

I made use of the existing brief bibliographic references compiled by Vasile Țelea and Luminița Machedon⁷. The engagement with the specialized literature was complemented by field research to photograph and document the known buildings that have survived to the present from

⁵ Luminița Machedon, Florin Machedon, „Arhitectura modernă românească a anilor 1920-1940”, in Beldiman, Cârneli, *Bucharest anii 1920–1940 : între avangardă și modernism / Bucharest in the 1920s–1940s: Between Avant-Garde and Modernism*, Catalogue of the exhibition of the same name, 1993, Simetria Publishing, Bucharest, 1993, pp. 69–90.

⁶ To be found at adt.arcanum.com

⁷ Țelea op cit, Machedon op. cit

the architect's built portfolio. The investigation of his architectural activity was further enriched by identifying individuals from his professional circle, as well as from intellectual milieus closely connected to the architect.

Additionally, the documentation included an examination of legislative projects that specifically targeted the activities of the Jewish community, relevant memoirs for the present study, and theoretical works with a direct impact on the architecture of the period—tools that allow for a deeper understanding of the context in which Jean Văleanu worked and evolved. Furthermore, I was able to document part of Văleanu's output in the visual arts, through the analysis of works exhibited in a retrospective exhibition in Paris in 1999, including a reference in the contemporary press to his artistic activity in an article dating from 1936.

I consider that this study brings new elements that can serve as a starting point for future research on Jean Văleanu's contributions to the capital's artistic and architectural heritage.

CHAPTER 1: The Architect's Life in the Political and Social Context of 20th-Century Bucharest

Jean Văleanu was born on 5 November 1904 in Bucharest, at 15 Stella Street, the son of Milo Văleanu (33 years old) and Julia Schaffer (22 years old)⁸. Regarding his family background, it is known to date that his parents were of Jewish origin. His father, originally from Târgu Neamț, received Romanian citizenship in 1891—an indication that he was one of the 888 Jews who participated in the War of Independence⁹. His father married Julia Schaffer in 1902¹⁰, and changed his name from Șmil Văleanu to Milo Văleanu¹¹. The action was likely intended to avoid the consequences of the antisemitic currents of opinion specific to the era. Milo Văleanu is known as a merchant and is mentioned in an article in *Dimineața* regarding a conviction for fraud, for which he was later acquitted¹². In a separate article in the *Universul* newspaper from 1928, a Milo Văleanu is mentioned as a lawyer in Ilfov County—therefore, the profession of the architect's father has not been definitively clarified to date.¹³

After graduating from the Matei Basarab High School in Bucharest in 1924 and from the School for Reserve Officers (1924–1925)¹⁴, Jean Văleanu urmează cursurile Politehnicii din Milano. Jean Văleanu attended the Polytechnic University of Milan. He obtained his architect's diploma in 1929, which he had recognized as equivalent in Bucharest in 1930¹⁵ (to be found in the appendix, Figure 167). In 1931, he enrolled in the Architects' Association, which granted him the right to practice professionally.

⁸ According to the Extract from the Birth Register of 1904, no. 7053, Romanian National Archives, file no. 2335.

⁹ According to Naturalization Ordinance no. 11, Minute no. 1062/22.01.1919, as well as the supporting document equivalent to the birth certificate no. 1948/19.04.1891 issued by the Târgu Neamț City Hall—found in file no. 2335 of the Romanian National Archives.

¹⁰ *Adevărul*, year 15, number 4657 dated 18.07.1902, p. 3

¹¹ *Universul*, year 20, number 252 dated 14.09.1902, p. 3

¹² *Dimineața*, year 5, number 1519 dated 11.05.1908, p. 2 and year 5, number 1557 dated 18.06.1908, p. 2

¹³ *Universul*, number 167 dated 22.07.1928

¹⁴ Vasile Florea, "Văleanu Jean" in *Enciclopedia artiștilor români contemporani*, volume 5, Arc 2000 Publisher, Bucharest, 2000, page 197

¹⁵ Graduation diploma, Romanian National Archives holdings, file no. 2335, noted in the *Official Gazette* no. 111 of 17.05.1933.

In the same year he graduated, Jean Văleanu marries future visual artist Stela Tomberg¹⁶ (mentioned in the period press as Steluța or Stella), who established a dowry upon marriage in the amount of 1,100,000 lei¹⁷ – indicating wealthy origins. According to references in the *Official Gazette* and other similar publications, Stela Tomberg came from the family of a merchant dealing in furs and imported clothing from Austria—Filip or Philippe Tomberg, the company *Tomberg et Schaffer* with its headquarters in downtown Bucharest, at Lipscaeni 84¹⁸. It is also noteworthy that Filip Tomberg was a member of a Jewish charitable society. „Mila și Ajutorul” (English – Mercy and Benefit, or *Ghemilut Chasadim*)¹⁹, as well as an auditor of the Bucharest Cultural Center²⁰, thus likely holding a prominent role within the Jewish community. Subsequently, Stela Văleanu is noted in the press of the years 1933–1957 as a visual artist engaged in bookbinding, costume design for theatrical productions, and the decorative arts²¹, with participations in group exhibitions in the country, as well as in biennials and triennials abroad.

The economic, social, and political context of the years 1929–1930, when the architect returned to the country, was marked by an economic flourishing of the capital, accompanied by significant demographic growth. The Statistical Yearbook of the Municipality of Bucharest indicated a 20% population increase between 1931 and 1936²². The, sizable, well-organized Jewish community held positions across a range of professional, intellectual, and artistic fields, in which they came to occupy a proportionally significant presence.

Upon Jean Văleanu’s return to Romania in 1929, the recognition of his studies in Milan, and his admission to the Architects’ Association in 1931²³ he began a career as an architectural entrepreneur. The architect began designing and building mostly residential dwellings, which were subsequently sold under his own management, with some transactions carried out by his

¹⁶ Table of marriage project declarations received and registered at the Civil Status Office of this sector from 17 to 23 October inclusive, *Municipal Gazette of the Municipality of Bucharest*, Year XXVIII, No. 43, 27 October 1929, page 14.

¹⁷ *Argus*, number 4985 dated 21.11.1929

¹⁸ *Monitorul Oficial*, volume I dated 01.03.1931, *Prezentul Economic, Financiar, Social*, no. 342 dated 22.03.1936, *Argus*, no. 6607 dated 17.04.1935

¹⁹ *Monitorul Oficial*, nb. 9 dated 09.01.1937, *Gazeta*, year III, no. 844 dated 01.01.1937

²⁰ *Argus*, nb. 7715 dated 21.12.1938

²¹ Ionel Jianu et al, op.cit, page 179

²² *Anuarul statistic al municipiului Bucharest 1931–1936*, Rotativa S.A.R., Bucharest, p. VIII

²³ *Monitorul Oficial*, no. 111 dated 17.05.1933, Ministerial communications and circulars, Table of licensed architects registered in the Body of Architects of Romania as of 09 May 1932, page 3460

wife. Against this backdrop of relative economic prosperity, Jean Văleanu designed and constructed, according to his file at the Romanian Union of Architects, over 60 buildings, most of them residential. His contemporary prestige likely facilitated the commission of three projects for theaters and cinemas, including the Excelsior, the Modern, and the C. Notarra film studio.

During World War Two, considering the economic contraction, worsening social conditions, and the temporary establishment of a nationalist regime marked by antisemitic measures, Jean Văleanu's design activity—and that of other Jewish architects, particularly in terms of initiating new construction projects—slowed significantly.

It should be noted, in this context, that a handwritten declaration by the architect to the Dean of the Romanian Union of Architects has been identified²⁴, stating that his Romanian citizenship could not be reviewed under Decree-Law no. 169 of 22 January 1938 concerning the Law on the Revision of Citizenship²⁵. These measures, enacted through antisemitic decree-laws, aimed to exclude Jews from public service, liberal professions, and professional associations—including the Architects' Association—and to revoke Romanian citizenship. In this context, it is likely that, initially, Jean Văleanu's citizenship was not revoked. Subsequently, on 11 October 1940, the architects' society temporarily excluded Jewish architects. Although the text of the decrees does not explicitly mention this association, the measure is documented in Mackenzie Douglas's history of Art Deco architecture, based on records from the Romanian Union of Architects²⁶.

In response to these measures, according to the same source, since Jewish architects were deprived of the right to sign their own projects, the Jewish community reportedly established a Jewish college at the Abason School (1940–1941), and subsequently at the Martin Bercovici Technical School. No references to Jean Văleanu in connection with this college have been identified; the only names known to me as participants are Harry Stern, Zigu Rapaport, and Jean Monda, the latter later becoming an associate of Jean Văleanu²⁷.

Regarding known events involving the architect, a mention was identified in the contemporary newspapers of a fire that broke out at the architect's materials depot at 3 Arcului

²⁴ Handwritten statement no. 173 of 31 January 1939, National Archives of Romania Fund, file no. 2335

²⁵ Published in *Monitorul Oficial*, anul 56, no. 18 dated 22.01.1938, available at <https://dspace.bcuculuj.ro>

²⁶ Mackenzie Douglas, *Înainte să se prăbușească. Modernism și Art Déco în Bucharest*, Humanitas, Bucharest, 2024

²⁷ *Ibidem*, op.cit, loc.cit

Street on 15 January 1940—an incident likely caused by an antisemitic attack, characteristic of the fascist fanaticism of the period²⁸.

Subsequently, under Decree-Law no. 2030/1941 concerning the military status of Jews²⁹, Jean Văleanu was mobilized within the Romanian National Army, in the forced labor detachments of the former Employers' Council, supervised by Sergeant Constantin Frățescu (nicknamed “The Little Marshal”)³⁰. The officer was later tried for war crimes and atrocities, during which Jean Văleanu testified; his statements were reproduced verbatim in contemporary newspaper articles³¹. According to his own statements, the Jews in Sergeant Frățescu's detachment were forced to supply him with luxury goods, and those who resisted were “beaten, tortured, and subjected to the most exhausting labor.” The military supervisor “extracted money from the Jews” and, to intimidate them, recounted as examples the massacres in which he had participated in Bessarabia, in detachments led by Ion Antonescu³².

Jean Văleanu's name appears on the list of donors to the Romanian Army on 22 August 1941, with a donation that was likely not voluntary, in accordance with the legislation of the period, under which Jews were required to pay an amount ten times higher to support the army—an aspect documented in the work of Leon Volovici³³ and as documented in the memoirs of Cella Serghi³⁴, and those of Mihail Sebastian³⁵) consisting of 19 bonds valued at 100,000 lei (an amount equivalent to one-eighth of the price of an apartment at that time), this “donation” suggests that the architect was in a relatively comfortable financial position at the outset of the Antonescu regime)³⁶.

Between 1941 and 1943, Jean Văleanu ceases to be mentioned in the newspapers—having previously been a frequent name, particularly in Jewish-sponsored press outlets, which were suppressed following the antisemitic repression measures of the regime. The exception is

²⁸ *Porunca Vremii*, year 9, no. 1550 dated 15.01.1940, p.5 and *Timpul* no. 970 dated 15.01.1940, p.13

²⁹ Published in *Monitorul Oficial* no. 164 dated 14.07.1941, available at <https://dspace.bcucluj.ro>

³⁰ *Universul-Provincie*, year 62, no. 157 dated 14.07.1945, *Universul-Provincie*, year 62, no. 159 dated 16.07.1945, page 3, *Ultima Oră*, year 2, no.245 dated 15.07.1945, page 1, *Timpul*, no. 2885 dated 14.07.1945 and 2887 dated 16.07.1945, page 5, *România Liberă* no. 289 dated 14.07.1945, no. 291 dated 16.07.1945 and 293 dated 19.07.1945

³¹ *România Liberă*, no. 291 dated 16.07.1945 and 293 dated 19.07.1945, *Scânteia*, no. 276 dated 16.07.1945, *Timpul*, nr. 2887 dated 16.07.1945

³² *Ibidem*

³³ Leon Volovici, *Ideologia naționalistă și <<problema evreiască>> în România anilor '1930*, Humanitas publishing house, Bucharest, 1995

³⁴ Cella Serghi, *Pe firul de păianjen al memoriei*, Polirom publishing house, Bucharest, 2013

³⁵ Mihail Sebastian, *Jurnal 1935-1944*, Humanitas publishing house, Bucharest, 2016

³⁶ *Timpul*, no. 1540 dated 22.08.1941

found in references within the files of the Special Commission for Adjudicating the Concealment of Jewish Property, Rights, and Interests, and for Repressing Sabotage of the Romanianization Process, where most of the architect's transactions were deemed fictitious³⁷. These measures, like the purported donations to the army, effectively constituted the confiscation of property held by the Jewish minority, adding to the broader framework of repression.

In the context of the establishment of communist governments and the Romanian–Soviet friendship, Jean Văleanu became a party member, as well as a member of the Romanian Association for Strengthening Ties with the Soviet Union (ARLUS)³⁸. In this context, he is mentioned in 1945 as a participant in the meeting of the Romanian Architects' Society held in honor of Soviet architects, organized by ARLUS, where he appeared alongside other prominent figures in the field—Professor Architect Petre Antonescu, Professor Ion Alexandru Davidescu, Titu Evolceanu, Gheorghe Simotta, Ion Ghica-Budești, Emil Nădejde, Pompiliu Macovei, Herman (Harry) Stern, and Nicolae Bădescu³⁹. We assess that the decision to join ARLUS and other official bodies was motivated by the need for physical and professional survival. His inclusion among prominent names in the profession indicates the recognition he enjoyed at the time. His decisions to register with official institutions were followed by the participation of both him and his wife in sanctioned artistic activities—Jean Văleanu, for instance, took part in the major official painting and sculpture exhibition at Sala Dalles after 23 August 1944, contributing two paintings, one of which was acquired by the Bulandra Theatre⁴⁰; (the exhibition has not been identified to date), while his wife, Stela Văleanu, subsequently participated in exhibitions at international salons as a representative of Romania⁴¹, which was probably an outcome of Jean joining the forums deemed reliable by Communist authorities.

During the brief period of reconstruction and optimism between the end of the war and the establishment of the communist regime, Jean Văleanu is recorded as a participant in a meeting of the Central Commission for Studies and Planning of the National Popular Party,

³⁷ *Viața*, dated 12.03.1943, page 3; *Viața*, no. 696 dated 25.03.1943; *Timpul*, no. 2110 dated 25.03.1945; *Curentul*, no. 5408 dated 08.03.1943; *Argus*, no. 897 dated 25.03.1943; *Curentul* no. 5384 dated 12.02.1943

³⁸ Handwritten statement no. 173 dated 31.01.1939, National Archives of Romania Fund, file no. 2335.

³⁹ *Universul-Capitala*, year 62, no. 188 dated 19.08.1945

⁴⁰ Teatrul Bulandra was contacted, replying they have not found a similar work in their fund.

⁴¹ Vasile Florea, op.cit., page 197, Ionel Jianu, op.cit., p. 179

presided over by Duiliu Marcu⁴², the meeting being titled “Rebuilding the Country and Planning the National Territory.” Other participants included engineers Cristea Niculescu, Petre Popescu, Claudiu Mititelu, Romulus Ianculescu, Alex Constantinescu, E. Petrovan (unidentified), Ștefan Lepădătescu, Gheorghe Ghemuleț, and Teodor Dobrescu. Many of these individuals were later incorporated into state institutions⁴³.

According to references to Văleanu identified in the holdings of the National Archives, between 1949 and 1951 he served as Director of Investments within the Ministry of Metallurgical Industry, joined ARLUS in 1951, and worked in the same ministry as a site manager⁴⁴. According to the same source, he is the author of the chapter “Industrial Architecture” in *Manualul arhitectului proiectant (Manual for practicing architects)*, volume number 1, published by Editura Tehnică in Bucharest in 1954 (a copy of the mentioned volume was not obtained).

From the brief biography noted by Vasile Florea in the Encyclopedia of Contemporary Artists (*Enciclopedia artiștilor contemporani*) it appears that the architect spent 12 years attempting to obtain a passport in order to travel to France to exhibit his visual artworks. In this context, Florea mentions alleged “harassment” by the security authorities⁴⁵. He emigrated permanently to Paris in 1961, where he remained until the end of his life⁴⁶. Also in 1961, he is mentioned in the *Official Gazette (Monitorul Oficial)* as having been awarded for outstanding contributions to the construction of socialism⁴⁷. This situation is ironic, considering his flight from the country shortly after being honored. This delay in granting a passport should not be readily attributed to the antisemitism of the period, as it was a relatively common practice aimed at restricting emigration. However, according to Liviu Rottman’s volume on the living conditions of the Jewish community at the time, the authorities were passive regarding the exodus of Jews, or opportunistic—seeking to condition emigration on the use of means provided

⁴² Described as a ‘propaganda satellite of the Romanian Communist Party’ in the study by George Neagoe, *G. Călinescu. The Rhetoric of ‘Democracy’ and ‘Democratization’ (1944–1946)*, *Transilvania*, year 120, no. 8, 01.08.2014, pp. 1–7.

⁴³ *Era Nouă*, number 499 dated 14.06.1946.

⁴⁴ Handwritten statement no. 173 dated 31.01.1939, National Archives of Romania Fund, file no. 2335.

⁴⁵ Vasile Florea, op.cit., page 197

⁴⁶ *Ibidem*

⁴⁷ *Official Bulletin of the Great National Assembly of the Romanian People’s Republic, Year X, No. 15, 24 June 1961, p. 223*

by Romania for travel⁴⁸). In this complex context, I contend that the denial of a passport to Jean Văleanu may have had multiple motivations, including his personal connections, some of which extended abroad, as well as the architect's lack of enthusiasm for actively promoting or supporting party politics and ideology.

I was able to reconstruct Jean Văleanu's economic activity within commercial enterprises, identifying his business partners and thus establishing a minimal network of professional relationships. In this context, a loan obtained by Jean Văleanu together with Gheorghe D.I. Creangă in 1937 has been identified⁴⁹ – (his business partner is known as a statistician and economist, founder of the newspapers *România Nouă* and *Economia Națională*, and author of numerous articles in *Epoca*, *Dimineața*, *Dreptatea*, and *Constructorul*⁵⁰). In 1935, Engineer Alfio Seny is noted as a business partner with whom he sold apartments at 19 Armenească Street and 23–25 Vasile Lascăr Street⁵¹; Seny is notorious as the first husband of famous novelist Cellei Serghi⁵² and employed in the 1950s as an engineer at the Institute for Hydrotechnical Construction Design. K. Davidovici is mentioned in 1934 as the engineer with whom Jean Văleanu designed the building at 16 Caimatei Street⁵³.

In 1938 Văleanu founds the Economic Society SARDAC⁵⁴ with the purpose of managing blockhouses and other buildings in Bucharest, together with Architect Toma Marinescu (a functionalist architect, graduate of the Bucharest School of Architecture in 1930⁵⁵), Marin Amzulescu (unidentified), lawyer Gheorghe Nicolescu (identified as a pleading attorney within the Litigation Department of the Autonomous Monopoly House⁵⁶), Lawyer Petru G. Pavelescu (unidentified), again Engineer K. Davidovici (unidentified, possibly the son of M. Davidovici, a leader of the Jewish community at the time), and lawyer Adrian Ghinea (attorney within the State Litigation Department of the Autonomous Administration of Metallurgical Industries and

⁴⁸ Liviu Rotman, *Evreii din România în perioada comunistă 1944-1965*, Polirom publishing house, Bucharest, 2004, pp. 13, 36

⁴⁹ *Argus*, year 27, no. 7197 dated 07.04.1937, page 2

⁵⁰ Biography of G.D. Creangă, available on the site of the Country Library of Brașov, available at <https://www.bjbv.ro/dictionar/creanga-gheorghe-d-i/>

⁵¹ *Argus*, year 27, no. 7190 dated 29.03.1937

⁵² Mihail Constantineanu, "La Balcic cu Cella Serghi și cei șapte balși", *România Literară*, no. 29 dated 04.07.1996, pp. 12-14

⁵³ *Dimineața*, year 28, no. 9095 dated 20.04.1932, page 4

⁵⁴ *Monitorul Oficial*, part a 2-a, no. 76 dated 01.04.1938

⁵⁵ Paul Constantin, *Dicționar universal al arhitecților*, Editura Științifică și Enciclopedică, Bucharest, 1986, p. 214

⁵⁶ *România-Provincie*, year 2, no. 253 dated 13.02.1939

Artillery Materials, reassigned in 1940 to the State Litigation Department of Teleorman County⁵⁷).

Similarly, in 1944 he partnered with a number of peers to establish the joint-stock company S.P.I.T., whose activities included the manufacture of technical, sanitary, electrical, and construction articles, as well as chemical products, and the import of industrial construction materials⁵⁸. His associates included Dumitru Gheorghiu, a chemist, and Engineer George G. Antonescu (director of the Association of Petroleum Enterprises for the Construction of Facilities Necessary for National Defense in 1942⁵⁹), Cezar Tacorian – a chemist at the Faculty of Sciences, University of Bucharest⁶⁰, Jean Ber – chemist; Ernest Silvan – engineer; Harsu Lupescu – engineer of Jewish origin; Jacques Singer, founder of the joint-stock petroleum company “Internova”⁶¹ and lawyer Enrico Elias, also an associate of the same company, Internova⁶², Mihail Steinfeld – chemist, director of the company Rompetrol in 1940⁶³, later referred to by the Communist Party press sources as a “hostile element”⁶⁴.

In 1945 Jean Văleanu founds the Economic Society SARBLOC, headquarters in str. Pia Brătianu nb. 8, together with Army General Nicolae Opran (known for liberal sympathies, possibly descended from a boyar family in Oltenia, and great-grandson of the cupbearer Gheorghe Opran⁶⁵), engineer C. Opran (unidentified, yet mentioned as a relative of the previous), Ecaterina Băleanu (unidentified), Wily Lipcovici (by profession a merchant, with no further information available), engineer Iulius Engler and architect Jean Monda (modernist architect, Romanian publicist, graduated the same university as Văleanu, Politecnico Milano, year 1924⁶⁶), with the stated scope of activity including the construction and operation of real

⁵⁷ *Monitorul Oficial*, part 1, year 108, no. 196 dated 26.08.1940

⁵⁸ *Monitorul Oficial*, part a 2-a, no. 255 dated 03.11.1944

⁵⁹ *Monitorul Oficial*, part a 2-a, no. 18 dated 22.01.1942

⁶⁰ According to the employee index in the database of the University of Bucharest Museum, accessed at muzeu.unibuc.ro/ro/fstiinte-indice-de-persoane on 3 May 2025

⁶¹ Dan Ovidiu Pantilie, „Istoricul Societății Anonime de Petrol «Internova» (1936-1938)”, in *Revista Centrului Cultural Pitești*, „Document – Restituiri”, year XIII, no. 3(37), new series 2015, pp. 12–18.

⁶² *Monitorul Oficial*, part a 2-a, no. 127 dated 02.06.1940

⁶³ *Monitorul Oficial*, part a 2-a, nuno.măr 189 dated 17.08.1940

⁶⁴ *România Liberă*, year 8, no. 1652 dated 11.01.1950

⁶⁵ Filip –Lucian V. Iorga, *Impactul Primului Război Mondial asupra descendenților boierimii române, proiect "Cultura română și modele culturale europene " de cercetare, sincronizare, durabilitate , cofinanced from FONDUL SOCIAL EUROPEAN, Muzeul Literaturii Române publishing house, Bucharest, 2014*

⁶⁶ Paul Constantin *op.cit.*, p. 230

estate, property transactions, and the trade and import of building materials ⁶⁷. As previously noted, Jean Văleanu designed, in partnership with Jean Monda, the buildings located at 29 Take Ionescu Street and 6 Eforie Street

Also in 1945, Jean Văleanu is mentioned as an administrator of the Romanian petroleum company ROCOL, alongside the lawyer Gabriel Steinberg (active in numerous import–export commercial companies) and the delegated administrator Gheorghe Petrescu (unidentified)⁶⁸ – It does not clearly result that this is the same Jean Văleanu, since during the same period a Jean Văleanu was active as prefect of Iași and another Jean Văleanu practiced as a lawyer in Ploiești.

In the same year, he founded the company SARPAC, whose scope of activity comprised construction carried out both on his own account and through public works contracting, acting as sole administrator. ⁶⁹ – In this case, it is certain that the reference concerns the architect Jean Văleanu.

In 1946, the architect receives a loan together with engineer Valter Handgriff (unidentified)⁷⁰.

The period was one of relative legislative relaxation and partial normalization, although antisemitic currents had not entirely disappeared from the broadly prevailing climate of opinion, which has been described at length as a systematic effort on the part of the administration and certain prominent representatives of the domestic intelligentsia⁷¹.

From death notices of close associates and family members, it is possible to reconstruct a familial and affinal network surrounding Jean Văleanu, potentially relevant in light of the dynamics of the Jewish community, thus, within the circle of the architect and his wife, as well as their extended families, appear Fany and Aron Feldman, Ernestina and Luca N. Luca, Otilia and Heinrich Schaffer, Isidor and Carolina Landau, and Herman Rafailovici⁷², Rovena and Alexandru S. Sanielevici (known as a physicist and corresponding member of the Romanian Academy), as well as the Grossmann, Rossin, Zissu families (including the family of Avram Leib Zissu, intellectual and leader of the Jewish community), the Pedvisocar family (descendants

⁶⁷ *Monitorul Oficial*, part a 2-a no. 182 dated 13.08.1945

⁶⁸ *Monitorul Oficial*, part a 2-a, no. 215 dated 21.09.1945

⁶⁹ *Argus* no.. 9575 dated 28.04.1945

⁷⁰ *Argus* no.. 9886 dated 14.06.1946

⁷¹ Leon Volovici, *op.cit.*

⁷² *Dimineața*, no.. 9416 dated 16.03.1933

of this family, including the sisters Anca Pedvisocar, a visual artist settled in New York, and Sanda Pedvisocar, settled in Paris, who maintained contact with them even after emigration), the Finkelstein and Kaufman families (settled in Paris, possibly facilitating their subsequent emigration), and the Dan Furcușteanu and Grun families⁷³.

The somewhat detailed aspects regarding the architect's professional development and his network of relationships indicate the prestige he enjoyed at the time as an entrepreneur, architect, and designer. This explains his presence within intellectual circles, even after the removal of the Legionary regime. Of particular significance is the wisdom showed by the architect while adapting to various regimes in order to continue practicing his profession under Communism, whose officials, at best, adopted an ambiguous and opportunistic stance toward the Jewish community.

Citing from the work of the historian Liviu Rotman, *in the brief transitional period preceding full communization, one can still speak of a certain normalization outside the political sphere. After having been excluded during the Antonescu period from all social activities, a number of Jewish specialists and technocrats—whether engineers, jurists, or economists—returned and began to play an important role in the postwar reconstruction of Romanian society*⁷⁴

This is the broader context in which we situate his brief activity on the Commission attached to the National Popular Party in 1947, alongside numerous other significant figures in Romanian culture and architectural history—for example, Petre Antonescu and Duiliu Marcu. However, we assess that the circles he frequented, both Jewish and liberal, likely contributed to his monitoring by the Securitate, as well as the delay in obtaining a passport—testimony to which can be found in Jean Văleanu's biographical references recorded by Vasile Florea⁷⁵.

We recall here a period of difficulty endured by the architect, who was excluded from the Union of Romanian Architects in 1958–1959 due to an alleged “delay in paying his membership fee.” In the explanation he provided to the Dean of the U.A.R., Jean Văleanu noted that he had suffered from illness, which had diminished both his professional activity and his income. The episode remains at least uncertain, given the well-known methods employed by the authorities at

⁷³ *Dimineața*, no. 10106 dated 14.02.1935

⁷⁴ Liviu Rotman, *Evreii din România în perioada comunistă*, Polirom publishing house, Bucharest, 2004, p. 6

⁷⁵ Vasile Florea, op.cit, loc.cit.

that time with regard to “hostile elements”⁷⁶. We contextualize in this situation the exclusion of George Matei Cantacuzino from the U.A.R. in the same year (and likely during the same union meeting)—in his case, the exclusion was reportedly due to “unadopted projects” from the Union of Romanian Architects of architect G.M. Cantacuzino.

Worth noting, for some clarification of the measures, is that the architect George Matei Cantacuzino, who was in Iași during the final period of his life and had previously been detained for five years following a conviction for sabotage and undermining state order, and assigned to the Labor Colony at the Danube–Black Sea Canal, drafted correspondence contesting his exclusion by the Union of Romanian Architects, suggesting that these accusations did not reflect reality⁷⁷. We therefore assess that the 1958–1959 moment, in which both Jean Văleanu and G.M. Cantacuzino were excluded from the Union of Architects, more likely corresponds to measures aimed at removing elements who did not conform to the party line or were considered unfriendly to the regime. Nonetheless, we note that this presumption can only be confirmed through research in the resources available at the National Council for the Study of Securitate Archives.

Jean Văleanu settled in Paris with his wife in 1960, where he was quickly admitted to the Order of Architects, continuing his work as an architect in “the design of numerous buildings in Paris and its surroundings,” without “neglecting his activity as a painter”⁷⁸. According to the biographical details provided by Vasile Florea, after settling in Paris Jean Văleanu focused predominantly on his artistic activity—an account that contrasts with a notice in the official French registers, which indicate that his architectural office remained open and active until 1995⁷⁹. Only one building designed by Jean Văleanu in Paris is known: the Aviation Club on the Champs-Élysées, on which he collaborated with his wife Stela Văleanu, who created a large decorative panel⁸⁰.

Jean Văleanu was featured in a retrospective exhibition from 02–23.07.1999 at the Gen Paul studio and gallery in Paris (now inactive), with a series of reproductions of his works available in digital format, as well as a photograph of him with his wife at the vernissage. The

⁷⁶ Handwritten statement no. 173 dated 31.01.1939, National Archives of Romania fund, file nr. 2335

⁷⁷ Vlad Mitric-Ciupe, *G.M. Cantacuzino în dosarele Securității*, Vreamea Publishing house, Bucharest, 2018

⁷⁸ According to the poster of the exhibit dated 1999, available at <https://www.flickr.com/photos/29253252@N07/with/3889548293>

⁷⁹ www.pappers.fr

⁸⁰ Vasile Florea, *op.cit.*, page 197, Ionel Jianu, *op.cit.*, pag. 179

architectural office is documented as active until 1995 at Paris, 18 Boulevard de Grenelle, 15e Arrondissement, 75015⁸¹, an address corresponding to the residence of Stela Văleanu in Ionel Jianu's volume on Romanian artists in the diaspora⁸². Jean Văleanu reportedly passed away in Paris on 23.04.2004⁸³. Figure 1 presents the chronology of Jean Văleanu's known activities during his time in Romania.

⁸¹ www.pappers.fr

⁸² Ion Jianu, *op.cit.*, *loc.cit.*

⁸³ https://www.ancestry.com/search/categories/34/?name=_valeanu

CHAPTER 2: Romanian architecture in modern context

The prolific activity of architect Jean Văleanu unfolded within a context highly conducive to the large-scale construction of residential buildings. This framework was shaped by a convergence of social, administrative, legislative, and artistic conditions. The following section outlines the factors that enabled this surge in architectural production, a development that positioned Bucharest as one of the largest European ensembles of residential architecture distinguished by a coherent and relatively unified character, representative of modernism.

The Historical, Legislative, and Social Context of Architectural Production. The period following the Union of the Romanian Principalities and the formation of Greater Romania, in the aftermath of the First World War, was one of relative prosperity, as the major financial crash of 1933 did not significantly affect the Romanian economy. From this perspective, the economy remained comparatively robust, with both public and private capital available for investment in the real estate sector. Modernist single-family and collective housing thus stand as material evidence of one of the most prosperous phases in the history of the capital.

The country had fulfilled its historic objective of national unification, and its position among the victorious powers of the First World War alleviated the pressure of an internal and external political agenda to which national architecture might otherwise have been subordinated. Architecture was therefore released from overt political instrumentalization—unlike, for example, the Neo-Romanian style, which had responded to aspirations for identity-building and national affirmation, emphasizing *Românism* and the ethnic unity of the Romanian people. Under these conditions, the context enabled a direct alignment with the international modernist movement, then in full ascendance under the influence of avant-garde ideas.

Moreover, the legislative framework was a favorable one—a fact evidenced both by the specialized literature and by the notices published by the architect under study in the period press. This framework pertained, on the one hand, to the provision of construction loans for residential buildings (with numerous references identified in *Monitorul Oficial* and *Argus* during

the period under review to credits accessed by Jean Văleanu), and, on the other hand, to tax incentives facilitating the development and operation of residential constructions⁸⁴.

Another key precondition was the vision of the local administration, particularly during the mayoral mandates of Dem I. Dobrescu and Alexandru I. Donescu, which supported the bold proposals of specialists regarded as highly competent and exercised a firm influence over the city's urban development⁸⁵.

Similarly, a generation of architects returned to the country following their architectural studies at major European academic centers: Baruch (Boris) Silberman, Jean Văleanu, and Jean Monda completed their studies at the Politecnico di Milano in the 1920s; Marcel Iancu studied in Zurich, where he was affiliated with the Dada movement; while Horia Creangă, Lucia Demetrescu, Tiberiu Niga, Alexandru Zamphiropol, George Matei Cantacuzino, and others pursued their education in Paris⁸⁶. The elites and intellectuals were exposed to modern currents, displayed a clear appetite for renewal, and perceived the gap between local practices and contemporary approaches to shaping the urban landscape, a condition that facilitated the reception of modernism.

Architectural Currents, Innovations, and the Urbanistic Context of the Interwar Period (1920–1930). As in all artistic movements, there was a persistent simultaneity between the classicizing styles, heir to the French academicism of the previous century, and constructions in the Neo-Romanian style. Several architects became known for their skillful navigation between the historicist idioms of the early twentieth century and modernism⁸⁷ – an example being Duiliu Marcu. In this way, the modernist current also emerged as a reaction of the new generation to the conservative architecture of the early twentieth century.

The construction of residential buildings was a response to the demographic growth recorded during the period. The Statistical Yearbook of the Municipality of Bucharest indicates a

⁸⁴Luminița Machedon, Florin Machedon, „Arhitectura modernă românească a anilor 1920-1940”, în Beldiman, Cârnecki, *Bucharest anii 1920–1940 : între avangardă și modernism / Bucharest in the 1920s–1940s: Between Avant-Garde and Modernism*, catalogue of the same exhibit dated 1993, Simetria publishing house, Bucharest, 1993, pp. 69–90.

⁸⁵ *Ibidem*

⁸⁶ Paul Constantin, , *op.cit.*

⁸⁷ Luminița Machedon, , Florin Machedon, *op.cit.*

20% increase in the population between 1931 and 1936⁸⁸ – which generated a demand for residential buildings. The existing housing stock was not only insufficient but also fell short of the expectations of the middle class regarding residential comfort, whose aspirations were oriented toward acquiring a “*blokhaus*” where comfort was maximized according to the standards of the time⁸⁹. Demographic growth and technological advancement also led to an increase in the number of automobiles, necessitating the adaptation of traffic arteries⁹⁰.

The first decades of the twentieth century were marked by urban innovations. As Graziela Doicescu observes in her memoirs, the capital, following the First World War, was in a phase of reconstruction and progress. The construction of new, taller buildings was accompanied by the transition from gas lamps to aerial gas lighting and, subsequently, to electricity. Innovations also encompassed the modernization of sanitary installations through the expansion of the sewer network—privies “at the back of the yard” were relocated indoors, both in new constructions and in older buildings⁹¹. Comfort was defined by its conditions of habitation—namely, “air, light, and equal warmth in every corner of the dwelling”⁹².

Structural innovations in buildings were facilitated by the use of new materials. Luminița Machedon emphasizes, both in her doctoral dissertation, in the aforementioned article, and in her contribution to *Romanian Modernism: The Architecture of Bucharest 1920–1940*, the widespread use of reinforced concrete. This material, combined with the progressive spirit of investors, also enabled an increase in building height⁹³. A structural system composed of reinforced concrete frames allowed for flexibility in apartment layouts, the zoning of apartments, and varied floor plans across different levels of a building, according to the preferences of investors⁹⁴. Similarly, the use of new materials is highlighted in *Către o arhitectură a Bucureștilor*, the manifesto of the three modernist architects Horia Creangă, Octav Doicescu, and Marcel Iancu: “chromed metals, metals eternally protected from rust, marbles and synthetic

⁸⁸ Statistical Yearbook of the Municipality of Bucharest 1931–1936, Rotativa S.A.R., Bucharest, p. VIII..

⁸⁹ Graziela Doicescu, *Captivantul Bucharest interbelic*, Vremea Publishing house, Bucharest, 2008, pp. 5-6.

⁹⁰ Duiliu Marcu et. al., *Planul Director de Sistematizare al Municipiului Bucharest*, Editura Institutului Urbanistic al României, Bucharest, 1938.

⁹¹ *Ibidem*.

⁹² Octav Doicescu, „Spiritul arhitecturii Bucharestlor”, in Iancu, Creangă, Doicescu, *Către o arhitectură a Bucharestlor*, Asociația pentru urbanistica Bucharestlor, Editura Ziarului Tribuna Edilitară, 1935, p. 37

⁹³ Luminița Machedon, Ernie Scoffham, *Romanian Modernism, The Architecture Of Bucharest 1920–1940*, Editura MIT PRESS 1999; Luminița Machedon, Florin Machedon, *op.cit.* p. 163

⁹⁴ *Ibidem*.

stones, ingenious details, supercements and supersteels”⁹⁵. This complemented the already established use of glass, introduced in the nineteenth century.

Significant are also the systematization efforts of the architects and engineers of the period, as evidenced by the development of the *Planul Director de Sistemizare a Municipiului București* under the leadership of Duiliu Marcu, which brought substantial transformations to the capital, impacting the architectural articulation of buildings. Specifically, the 1935 plan, whose effects began to materialize in 1938, provided for: (a) the elimination of nonessential streets, (b) the widening of main thoroughfares, (c) expropriations, and (d) the demolition of old or unsuitable buildings, to be replaced by revenue-generating structures better suited to contemporary needs⁹⁶.

The same plan also outlined the characteristics of buildings appropriate to these objectives—multi-story residential buildings that allowed the concentration of citizens’ activities and the attainment of high levels of comfort at relatively low cost. The master plan introduced zoning, imposed building alignments, and regulated building heights, which could not exceed 24 meters (except for corner buildings, which, to mark intersections, could reach 36 meters). It also mandated aesthetic continuity between neighboring buildings and provisions for cross-ventilation⁹⁷.

The result of these legislative and urbanistic changes was a shift in the way architects related to the existing context and the built urban fabric. Parcels now regulated also in terms of subdivision provided opportunities for projects that were better integrated into the existing urban fabric, as well as for large-scale urban insertions. Moreover, buildings were aligned along an existing linear frontage, strictly determined by alignment and height regulations, while taller buildings featured successive setbacks at upper floors, playing a significant role in their compositional articulation. Subdivision and demolitions created large plots, allowing for buildings with façades positioned at the intersection of multiple thoroughfares or with multiple street-facing façades—resulting in a volumetric composition that was often more spectacular,

⁹⁵ Octav Doicescu, *op. cit.*, *loc. cit.*

⁹⁶ Duiliu Marcu et al, *Planul Director de Sistemizare al Municipiului Bucharest*, Editura Institutului Urbanistic al României, Bucharest, 1938

⁹⁷ *Ibidem*

fluid, and well-defined, exploring curved surfaces and, at times, combining volumes of varying forms⁹⁸.

Modernist Architecture in Bucharest, 1920–1930: From Ideals to Built Reality. The first three decades of the twentieth century were fertile ground for avant-garde movements and for the development of modernism in architecture, with certain publications playing a key role in the introduction of modernist ideas in the capital. These include:

Vers une architecture (1925) by Le Corbusier, the influential Belgian architect and both practitioner and theoretician of Modernism, introduced five key principles—though these were rarely implemented simultaneously in a single building. These principles include:

- a) **The pilotis-supported house**, which frees the ground floor and allows green spaces to continue beneath the building;
- b) **The roof terrace**, conceived as a green space, returning to nature and the occupants part of the land area otherwise occupied by the building's footprint;
- c) **The free plan**, which allows interior functions to be organized according to functional principles, independent of structural constraints; in this way, columns and beams enable innovative floor plans and the elimination of walls, resulting in a functional spatial arrangement;
- d) **Long, horizontal ribbon windows**;
- e) **The liberation of façades**, giving rise to façades with free design.

Le Corbusier advocated that **form should follow function**, embracing minimalism and rejecting ornamentation, promoting asymmetrical compositions and an emphasis on volumetric expression. He also championed the concept of garden cities, with skyscrapers concentrating large populations while freeing extensive land areas to be transformed into parks⁹⁹.

The daily *Contimporanul* appeared between 1922 and 1930, with Ion Vinea and the architect Marcel Iancu as editors. The magazine initially followed a constructivist agenda, drawing on European avant-garde ideas and popularizing the arts of the avant-garde movements. Issues 53–54 (1925) were dedicated to architectural themes, including the articles *Function and Form* and *The New Architecture*, which outlined directions for future projects. Issues 57–58

⁹⁸ Luminița Machedon, Florin Machedon, *op.cit.* p. 163

⁹⁹ Le Corbusier, *Vers une architecture*, Collection l'esprit nouveau, Les Editions Georges Cres, Paris, 1925

focused on interior architecture¹⁰⁰. Both issues include articles that engage with avant-garde ideas in architecture, reflecting the magazine's role in introducing these concepts to Romanian architectural discourse.

The manifesto *Către o arhitectură a Bucureștilor* appeared in 1935, signed by Marcel Iancu, Horia Creangă, and Octav Doicescu. The text adopts a number of principles and concepts from Le Corbusier. By highlighting aspects considered nonconformist with the conventions and demands of the time in terms of functionality and aesthetics, it asserts that:

“While technology, automobiles, electricity, and reinforced concrete assert their conquests, the city plan and the horizontal projection of properties remain unchanged; there exists an anarchy of styles and an incongruity and lack of harmony between adjacent buildings.”

The solution to these deficiencies is urbanism. However,

“A good plan of layout and alignment is not enough—you must first establish an architecture that renders the entire city a unified whole,”
achieved in

“the new style (...) the perfect accord of this geometric, undecorated, sober style with mechanized life,”

And

“only through a program of tall constructions (...) the house rises in height, leaving the ground free for gardens in the heart of the city”¹⁰¹.

In Section 1, Marcel Iancu argued that “*blokhaus*-es provide the possibility of: (i) widening streets, (ii) reducing unnecessary roadways, (iii) placing gardens between vertically concentrated residences, (iv) reducing the city's surface area through densification, and (v) achieving economic, sanitary, and comfort conditions unprecedented until today”¹⁰². The second section of the manifesto, signed by Horia Creangă, emphasizes the necessity of harmony within building ensembles, as well as simplicity, through “proportioned volumes transparent in space, straight lines, volumes without unnecessary ornamentation, horizontal ribbon windows, a sincere

¹⁰⁰ Luminița Machedon, Florin Machedon, *op.cit.*

¹⁰¹ Marcel Iancu, Horia Creangă, Octav Doicescu, “*Către o arhitectură a Bucharestlor*”, Asociația pentru urbanistica Bucharest, Editura Ziarului Tribuna Edilitară, 1935, pp. 1-3

¹⁰² Marcel Iancu, *Utopia Bucharestlor*, in Iancu, Creangă, Doicescu, “*Către o arhitectură a Bucharestlor*”, Asociația pentru urbanistica Bucharestlor, Editura Ziarului Tribuna Edilitară, 1935, pp. 1-19

and simple expression of modern needs, which conveys beauty through simplicity and utility through comfort”¹⁰³.

The impact of architecture and the responsibility of the architect in relation to the outcomes of their production are emphasized by Octav Doicescu in the final section of the manifesto, where he asserts that any “house or any exterior plastic element creates the city’s atmosphere. Since this atmosphere reverberates upon the people gathered in the city and shapes a kind of destiny for communal life, there must be responsibility and control. A constructed house that fails to fulfill at least the conditions of aesthetic correctness (...) diminishes the spirituality of both the individual and the city”¹⁰⁴.

It is equally evident that Le Corbusier’s ideas were partially adopted by Duiliu Marcu’s Master Plan for Bucharest (with the notable exception of the garden-city concept, which he deemed incompatible with the local spirit), as well as by the manifesto of the three modernist architects from Bucharest, while sections of his work were published in fragments in issues of *Contimporanul*.

This confirms both the Romanian architects’ familiarity with the principles of European currents and their deliberate intention to align themselves with the avant-garde trends of architectural practice. However, the modernist principles—whether aesthetic, structural, or functional—filtered through the specificities of local culture, did not exert a determining influence on the overall aesthetic structures and general planimetry. Nevertheless, the massive, large-scale expansion of modernism definitively shaped the capital’s urban silhouette¹⁰⁵.

It is worth noting that architecture, as a major art distinct from the visual arts, music, or literature, comparatively demonstrates weaker political engagement. Native architecture did not experience a phase that could be defined as avant-garde in the sense of being imbued with a subversive or oppositional impetus¹⁰⁶. This characteristic arises not only from the spirit of the period and the aforementioned factors, but also from the particular nature of architecture as a discipline that synthesizes art, science, and technology, shaped by social, historical, and

¹⁰³ Horia Creangă, *Anarhia stilurilor și arta viitorului*, în Iancu, Creangă, Doicescu , ”*Către o arhitectură a Bucurestilor*”, Asociația pentru urbanistica Bucurestilor, Editura Ziarului Tribuna Edilitară, 1935, pp. 18-32

¹⁰⁴ Octav Doicescu, *Spiritul arhitecturii Bucurestilor*, în Iancu, Creangă, Doicescu , ”*Către o arhitectură a Bucurestilor*”, Asociația pentru urbanistica Bucurestilor, Editura Ziarului Tribuna Edilitară, 1935, p. 37

¹⁰⁵ Luminița Machedon, Ernie Scoffiman, *op.cit.* pp. 3-4

¹⁰⁶ Luminița Machedon, Florin Machedon, *op.cit.*, p. 163

economic conditions¹⁰⁷. As evidenced by the manifestos and documents of the period, local architecture stemmed from the desire for progress and alignment with European civilization. Furthermore, Romanian architects acted independently, without forming collectives akin to the European avant-garde (*Bauhaus, De Stijl*)¹⁰⁸. Although the architects stand out as highly individualized personalities, there are overarching trends that indicate a unified manner in which they filtered modern influences coming from the European cultural sphere. There were also small groupings of architects, such as Duiliu Marcu’s workshop—himself being a prominent figure of interwar architecture—which brought together numerous architects (including George Matei Cantacuzino and Alexandru Zamphiropol), or the collaborations of Jean Văleanu and Jean Monda, exemplified by their joint project at Take Ionescu Street no. 29.

In Luminița Machedon’s study, these commonalities of interwar modernist architecture are synthesized as follows:

a) **Judicious use of the vertical and horizontal geometry of existing plots**, leading to functionally and aesthetically appropriate solutions and rational site utilization;

b) **Exploitation of right-angle potential**, alternations of rectangular forms and curved surfaces defining façades, shaping public space and the urban frame, embedding dynamic character;

c) **Emphasis on the horizontal**, alternating with vertical elements, particularly visible through large glazed surfaces in ribbon-window compositions;

d) **Marked simplicity**, expressed through pure volumes, formal precision, and freedom from decorative or ornamental features;

e) **Careful selection of detail elements**, where objects of functional value are transformed into an aesthetic specific to this current, especially within the Art Deco-inflected strand of modernism¹⁰⁹.

The characteristics outlined above are also reflected, as I will detail in the following chapter, in the architectural projects of Jean Văleanu—combining a keen intelligence in the use of the plot, free-form drawing in façade design, the “small” details that enliven the projects, and compliance with the urban regulations imposed by Duiliu Marcu’s Master Plan.

¹⁰⁷ *Ibidem, op.cit, loc.cit.*

¹⁰⁸ Luminița Machedon, Florin Machedon, *op.cit.*, p. 163

¹⁰⁹ *Idem, op.cit, loc.cit.*

CHAPTER 3. Activitatea arhitecturală a lui Jean Văleanu în România

Methodology and Research Resources. The research on the architect's activity included extensive archival work in the holdings of the Romanian National Archives (references to his work are found in File no. 2335), the Union of Architects of Romania, and the special collections of both the National Library of Romania and the Central University Library of Cluj-Napoca. Documentation also involved the search for photographs and postcards of the buildings in the Cabinet of Prints at the Romanian Academy Library, Bucharest branch, as well as in the photographic holdings of the Museum of Bucharest—Palatul Suțu—and in the Special Collections of the Central University Library of Cluj-Napoca.

Documenting was complemented by primary research in the holdings of the Bucharest City Hall, specifically in the file of the building at Calea Victoriei 101, known as Blocul Domnica. Archival data were confirmed or supplemented through investigation of references to the architect in the period press, as well as by cross-referencing buildings mentioned in Vasile Țelea's *Dictionary of Architects*¹¹⁰.

Of the sixty buildings designed by Jean Văleanu, thirty have been identified and catalogued. Some of these no longer exist—such as Blocul Casata (Take Ionescu, now General Gh. Magheru no. 26), the building at Piața Kogălniceanu no. 5, and the Excelsior Cinema (Academiei no. 28–30)—demolished either during the Allied bombings of 1944 or as a consequence of the 1977 earthquake. Several other buildings have been renovated, with interventions preventing an accurate understanding of the original design; examples include the addresses Sfântul Elefterie no. 18, Splaiul Unirii 56–58 (Intrarea Ursulețului), and Lucaci 29 (today Matei Basarab no. 27). To identify current addresses, the 2022 street nomenclature published by the Bucharest City Hall was consulted. All known buildings were documented through exterior photography, and in some cases, interior photography as well. A classification was compiled according to chronology, stylistic characteristics, and location.

Some addresses could not be identified—Pache no. 1, Romană no. 76, Gheorghe Coșbuc no. 27, and Robert de Flers 47 (these names have historically been applied to multiple streets in the capital, and no buildings from the period under study or attributable to the architect are

¹¹⁰ Vasile Țelea, *Personalități ale arhitecturii românești 1880-2010*, volume 2 L-Z, Rentrop & Straton, Bucharest, 2023, p 412

currently located at these addresses), nor twelve buildings presumed to have been designed by the architect in the Cotroceni neighborhood. At the addresses Pieptănari 83–85 and Cometei no. 12, no buildings presently exist. By far, the greatest challenge was tracing parcels that had been subdivided and resold from those originally acquired, upon which Văleanu’s projects were subsequently constructed. This situation applies to a series of addresses, such as Romană no. 76 and Pieptănari 83–85, parcels for which construction permits were obtained, allowing a resell of lots for higher prices.

The main conclusion from the documentation of existing buildings is that architect Jean Văleanu worked exclusively in a modernist style, with variations specific to Art Deco. The large number of sixty buildings recorded in the architect’s file at the Union of Architects of Romania, designed over a relatively short period (1932–1947, i.e., fifteen years), attests to a remarkable capacity for effort and imagination. The stylistic choices throughout his career as both architect and developer, and his solutions for spatial organization and design through innovations characteristic of Art Deco, justify his recognition as an Art Deco architect. A clear receptivity is also observed to compositional elements specific to Streamline Moderne, the International Style, and Expressionism in architecture.

Grouping of Buildings by Function. Of the thirty documented buildings, the majority are medium- and large-scale *blokhaus*-type residential buildings, but the portfolio also includes theaters and cinemas: the Modern Theater at Constantin Mille 14; the Excelsior Theater at Strada Academiei 28–30; the Constantin Notarra cinema studio—presumed to be the Cinema Studio at Take Ionescu/Magheru no. 29—and the Eforie Cinema on the street of the same name—the latter two being joint projects with the architect Jean Monda. Additionally, in 1934, his contribution to the design of the Vesel (n.n. Happy/Comical) Theater is recorded, housed in a small hall within the Palatul Eforiei Spitalelor at Elisabeta no. 5 (today 27–29).

Chronological Grouping. The architect’s earliest residential projects, dating from 1932–1934, are medium-sized buildings with four to ten apartments, appearing primarily in the Armenian-Jewish neighborhood. This typology remained a constant throughout his entire design career in Romania. Beginning in 1935, he also designed and constructed collective or revenue-generating buildings with more than sixty apartments, located in the Armenian-Jewish, Izvor-Kogălniceanu, and Calea Victoriei neighborhoods. Following the Second World War, in the

period preceding the establishment of the communist regime, two large-scale revenue buildings were identified, constructed in collaboration with the architect Jean Monda. These projects feature similarly treated façades and include a cinema on the ground floor—Eforie 6 and Take Ionescu 29.

Grouping by Areas of the Capital. Most of the architect’s known projects are located, according to the map of buildings designed in the capital (source: own research, Figure 2), in the Armenian-Jewish neighborhood, with the majority of transactions throughout his career involving clients with Jewish family names. Leisure-oriented buildings are situated along central thoroughfares—Magheru-Bălcescu, Academiei, Eforie, and Constantin Mille—while a number of residential buildings from the period 1935–1938 are located on Calea Victoriei, Plevnei, and Take Ionescu.

Grouping by Building Size. Defining features of the architect’s work include a creative approach to the Art Deco style, as well as the prolific and diverse solutions applied to challenging plots.

Medium-Sized Buildings. These buildings, ranging from two to four stories, contain limited numbers of apartments. They are walk-up revenue buildings (without elevators) and flat roofs; the upper floors frequently feature setbacks, a consequence of urban planning regulations, which justify the stepped compositions characteristic to Art Deco. The smaller scale provides a framework for the plastic articulation of façades—highlighting the stairwell with a skylight, and emphasizing this ensemble through vertical or horizontal slit windows or “bitten” corner windows.

The “comb” recess appears frequently—a multi-story projecting bay extended with parapets at each level, often employing an aerodynamic line. Parapets, often reduced in height, give way to metal balustrades that articulate the recess. The portals of these buildings exhibit the highest degree of expressiveness, confirming the notion that Art Deco portals feature unique combinations of motifs. The main stairwell and entrance hall become representative elements, thanks to careful attention to high-quality materials and detailing. The wide variety of portals is achieved through the interplay of Art Deco motifs in the metalwork—zigzags, sunbursts, and transverse geometric patterns—that articulate, complete, and define the building. The framing of the main entrances is occasionally resolved with quarter-cylinder transitions. High-quality

materials, used both inside and out, ensure durability: frosted glass surfaces, marble, terrazzo, monochrome or polychrome flooring, chrome-plated stainless steel hardware, finely executed recessed and coffered wall fixtures, and integrated lighting elements. Medium-sized buildings are representative of the architect's work during the period 1932–1939.

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Medium sized buildings

3. Comb like setback, Armenească 19

4. Streamline, flat roof, parapet railings Thomas Masaryk 9

5. Colț ”mușcat”, Argentina 33

6. Chamfered corner Caimatei 16

7. Portal with decorative metalwork, mosaic concrete, monochromatic design Ferdinand 17

8. Multi-level elevated bay marking the main entrance, comb-like setback, corner windows, upper floors with recesses, Pța Kogălniceanu 7-8

Small-Sized Buildings. Two such buildings are known, constructed in tandem in 1938 in the *pachebot* style, on a plot located between Victor Babeş and Frederic Joliot Curie streets. Research conducted among residents confirmed that the two buildings were constructed simultaneously, a conclusion supported not only by stylistic analysis but also by the materials used. Uniquely, to the best of my knowledge, the two buildings at Victor Babeş 1 and 5, situated at the ends of the plot, frame the central building in parentheses, creating a composition that reads as a cohesive *pachebot* ensemble even when viewed from the street’s perspective. The project at no. 1, famously known as the Boat House, is a two-family residence with separate entrances, adhering to the original design. Its defining features of the *pachebot* style include characteristic ribbon windows, an elongated footprint, upper-floor setbacks, aerodynamic lines, the absence of ornamentation, the use of the building material itself as ornament, and a light color palette.

Figure 9. Map showing the location of small-sized buildings, highlighting the tandem *pachebot* ensemble on Victor Babeş Street.

The project at no. 5 comprises a ground floor plus three stories, featuring horizontal and vertical setbacks; the Streamline aesthetic dominates the main façade, emphasizing the street corner. Corner connections extend symmetrically through a double “comb”-type projection with undulating parapets and balustrades similar to those of the building at no. 1. The main façade features a concave wall contrasting with the convex line of the projection, which articulates the façade in a defining manner. The entrance portal on Frederic Joliot Curie Street contains metalwork with geometric patterns, contrasting with the aerodynamic line of the handle.

Interior photographs reveal the use of terrazzo in black-and-white contrast on the steps, as well as mosaic surfaces. Access from Victor Babeş Street, concealed by vegetation, is marked by a convex vertical slit articulating the stairwell with metal ribs. Notable is the alternation of horizontal slits with simple windows, and the marking of the bay window with a hexagonal-section skylight, echoing the console forms of the bay. The alternation of *calcio vecchio* plaster with granite panels, the interplay of solid and void, concave and convex forms, and the skylight compensates, in a modernist spirit, for the absence of other decorative effects. These two

buildings demonstrate the virtually limitless possibilities of decorative materiality and the use of form itself as ornament in Streamlined Deco. Field research also suggested the possible existence of another *pacobot*-style building by Jean Văleanu on Mihai Eminescu Street (number not identified at this stage, possibly corresponding to the building historically recorded at the postal address Strada Romană no. 76).

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**Small-scale buildings –
pachebot style**

10. Main facade - rendering,
Victor Babeş 1

11. Streamline - rendering,
Victor Babeş 1

12. Facade, typical corner
for a Streamlined Deco,
ribbon windows, Victor
Babeş 1

13. Streamline corner,
alternating convex and
concave forms, Victor
Babeş 5

14. Portal with decorative
metalwork, metalwork on
the tympanum, mosaic
concrete, monochromatic
Victor Babeş 5

15. Streamline corner,
Comb-like setback, parapet
railings, alternating concave
and convex forms of the
parapet and door, Victor
Babeş 5

Large-Sized Buildings. Comprising between sixty and one hundred apartments, these buildings are located in the Armenian-Jewish neighborhood and along central arteries—Calea Victoriei 101, Take Ionescu/Magheru 26 and 29, Vasile Lascăr 23–25, Maria Rosetti 36, and Calea Plevnei 1. Large-scale projects began in 1935 and followed a consistent design and development trajectory: the acquisition of the plot by the architect, design and construction of the buildings, followed by the sale of apartments either independently or through real estate agencies (most frequently, architect Jean Văleanu was assisted by the Modern Agency).

These buildings can be further subdivided into **infill-type buildings**, constructed within an existing urban fabric along a fixed alignment with a restricted height regime (such as Blocul Domnica on Calea Victoriei, erected in 1938, as well as the collaborative projects with Jean Monda at Take Ionescu/Magheru 29 and Eforie 6, which share similar stylistic treatments of the façade), and **corner buildings**, erected at the intersection of two or more streets. This second category includes the buildings at Take Ionescu/Magheru no. 26 (Bloc Casata, 1937, historically referred to as the “Blok Văleanu”), Calea Plevnei 1 (Blok Lazăr, 1935), and Maria Rosetti 36, whose dominant Streamline line emphasizes the small square formed at the intersection of Maria Rosetti, Armenească, and Logofăt Luca Stroici streets (formerly Strada Robert de Flers).

Stylistically, the large-scale projects can be divided into two categories: **Art Deco with Streamline influences** (Vasile Lascăr 23–25, Maria Rosetti 36) and **International Style–Functionalist with Deco accents**—as in the buildings Casata, Take Ionescu 26, and Calea Plevnei 1—which feature clear lines, articulated verticals, and the juxtaposition of horizontal and vertical planes, treated externally with white plaster characteristic of purism and rationalism. The building at Vasile Lascăr 23–25 exhibits horizontal slits and ribbon windows, while parapets are articulated with decorative metal balustrades (Calea Victoriei 101). Buildings realized in collaboration with Jean Monda share a common façade treatment, divided into alternating registers decorated with rustication and setbacks. In the case of Blok Casata and Blok Lazăr, vertical accents are articulated either through corner windows or, counterintuitively, through solid wall sections, achieved by the absence of windows. Parapet panels, simple and austere, are fitted with balustrades (Calea Victoriei, Calea Plevnei, Take Ionescu 26). The absence of ornament is compensated for through the treatment of form itself as ornament.

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Large sized buildings

16. Main faade with simplified treatment, polygonal corner plan, Calea Plevnei 1 (Blok Lazăr), highlighting Streamlined Deco articulation.

17. Main faade with aerodynamic lines and alternation of solid and void, Maria Rosetti 36, reflecting Streamlined Deco principles.

18. Corner building with pronounced vertical accents, Take Ionescu 26 (Blok Casata), exemplifying Streamlined Deco articulation.

Faade articulated in alternating registers with horizontal emphasis, highlighted through rustication and grouped openings, featuring a ribbon window.

19. Take Ionescu 29

20. Eforie 6

Stylistic grouping. Jean Văleanu’s projects occupy a confluence of styles, reflecting the mutual influence of mature Art Deco, Streamline, Expressionism, and the International Style. The following presents a classification of the known buildings by category, shown in Figure 21.

Influence Style	Mature Art Deco	Streamline	International Style / Functionalism
Mature Art Deco	Teatru Modern/ C-tin Mille, 14/1936 ; Lucaci 29/1936 ; Pța Kogălniceanu 5 și 7-8/1935 ; D. Onciul 29/1934 ; Caimatei 16/1932	Argentina 33/1940; Th Masaryk 9/1939; Vasile Lascăr 23-25/1937; Al. Donici 36/1937; Maria Rosetti 36/1935; Armenească 19/1935; Ferdinand 17/1933	Călușei 20-22/1936
Streamline	//////////////////////////////////// //////////////////////////////////// ////////////////////////////////////	Victor Babeș 1, Victor Babeș 5/1938; Calea Moșilor 86/1934;	//////////////////////////////////// //////////////////////////////////// ////////////////////////////////////
Expressionism	Aron Florian 4bis/1934	//////////////////////////////////// //////////////////////////////////// ////////////////////////////////////	//////////////////////////////////// //////////////////////////////////// ////////////////////////////////////
International Style / Functionalism	Take Ionescu 29/1947; Ion Brezoianu 51/1945; Eforie 6/1945; Calea Victoriei 101/1938;	//////////////////////////////////// //////////////////////////////////// //////////////////////////////////// ////////////////////////////////////	Calea Plevnei 1/1935

Figure 21. **Stylistic Grouping of Buildings Constructed by Jean Văleanu**
Source: Author’s own research

Methodological Clarifications for the Stylistic Categories Used in the Proposed Grouping.

The stylistic categories or currents labeled as Mature Art Deco, Streamline, De Stijl motifs, and Expressionist accents in Romanian Art Deco architecture are drawn from the research of Mihaela Criticos, a specialist in Art Deco aesthetics. Her volume *Art Deco sau Modernismul bine temperat*, which builds upon her doctoral research, provides a framework for defining and identifying these stylistic categories. However, the aforementioned work also includes a disclaimer regarding the definition and attribution of the Art Deco style: „Any generalization becomes risky, and for every rule, countless exceptions can be found that contradict it. Familiar

forms and motifs are transformed and reinterpreted, introduced in new or unusual combinations, which unfold and recombine without adhering to any predetermined norm”¹¹¹.

The stylistic classification “**Mature Art Deco**” or “**Art Deco with Streamline influences**” is applied when a building, structurally or stylistically, predominantly exhibits the characteristics of a particular category—bearing in mind that no building constructed in Romania under Modernism fully embodies the features of Purism.

These categories are also drawn from the volume *B:MAD București / Bucharest Modernism Art Deco*, curated by Dragoș Dogaru, Mihaela Criticos, and Sidonia Teodorescu—a work whose structure is organized in part according to stylistic categories, where general or generic characteristics of each category are illustrated through buildings in the capital¹¹².

Expressionist influences in architecture, discussed in the volume *Art Deco sau Modernismul bine temperat* and illustrated through buildings in other countries as well as in Bucharest, include major innovations in the modeling of interior space¹¹³, the essentialization of form, reflecting and converging with Functionalist aesthetics¹¹⁴, pronounced plasticity and dynamic compositional tension¹¹⁵ as well as the adoption of the *pachebot* style, regarded as a synthesis of Art Deco, Expressionism, International Style principles, and American design trends of the period¹¹⁶. The incorporation of Expressionist elements is described by Mihaela Criticos in her volume *Ornament. Theme and Variations*, through an analysis of buildings designed by Marcel Iancu. These elements are primarily located in the façade composition (comparable, for instance, to the design by Jean Văleanu at Aron Florian 4bis) and are particularly evident in façades characterized by aerodynamic lines¹¹⁷. A similar position regarding Streamline is presented by Ana Maria Zahariade in *Themes of Architecture in Twentieth-Century Romania*¹¹⁸.

¹¹¹ Mihaela Criticos, *Art Deco sau Modernismul bine temperat*, Simetria Publishing house 2009, p. 167.

¹¹² Dragoș Dogaru, Mihaela Criticos, Sidonia Teodorescu, *B:MAD Bucharest/Bucharest Modernism Art Deco*, Association Igloo Habitat & Arhitectura, Bucharest, 2018.

¹¹³ Mihaela Criticos, *op.cit.*, p. 185.

¹¹⁴ Idem, *op.cit.*, p. 244.

¹¹⁵ Idem, *op.cit.*, *loc.cit.*

¹¹⁶ Idem, *op.cit.*, p. 249.

¹¹⁷ Mihaela Criticos, *Ornament. Temă și variațiuni*, Simetria, Bucharest, 2005, p. 16 și 126.

¹¹⁸ Ana Maria Zahariade, *Teme ale arhitecturii din România în secolul XX*, Editura Institutului Cultural Român, Bucharest 2003, p. 16.

Aspects related to the aesthetics of the International Style and its assimilation in Romanian architectural projects of the 1930s are extensively discussed in the research of Ana Maria Zahariade. According to the scholar, the International Deco style represents an expression of modernity that was far more accessible to Romanian society than the International Style itself¹¹⁹, To the extent that it assimilates the rigor of the latter, it favors simple geometric forms and clear articulation of horizontals, achieving a balanced relationship between horizontal and vertical elements, a complex volumetry, and a certain formal rhetoric, reinforced through carefully elaborated details¹²⁰. Buildings constructed in the International Style favor relationships of equality, even among volumes with different functions, assembling them in a “democratic” manner as bars articulated by vertical circulation¹²¹. A phenomenon visible in the architecture of the capital, the evolution of Deco aesthetics in the 1930s—particularly through the influence of Streamlining—moves toward the integrative vision of the International Style, producing buildings designed entirely for corner sites rather than merely offering partial corner solutions¹²². Regarding the major difference in façade composition between the International Style and Art Deco, Zahariade identifies the treatment of the entrance as a key criterion for stylistic attribution. In the International Style, entrances are often concealed in the shadow of pilotis or integrated into the monotonous rhythm of the glazing and window frames, whereas Deco architecture perpetuates the symbolic importance traditionally accorded to the entrance as a “threshold,” a “passage” into another space whose identity and values are expressed through the image of the portal¹²³. This criterion is confirmed by Jean Văleanu’s buildings. Specifically, large-scale International Style buildings, aligned along a predetermined street front, contain commercial spaces at the ground level and articulate the façade vertically in a “democratic” manner through the use of flutings, profiles, and moldings. The entrance portal is placed on a secondary plane, often masked or subtly integrated among other openings composed with sobriety and severity. In contrast, access to small-scale Mature Art Deco buildings affords a privileged position to the portal within the façade composition, typically accentuated through high-quality metalwork.

¹¹⁹ Idem, *op.cit.*, p. 233.

¹²⁰ Idem, *op.cit.*, *loc.cit.*

¹²¹ Idem, *op.cit.*, p. 224.

¹²² Idem, *op.cit.*, p. 213.

¹²³ Idem, *op.cit.*, p. 209.

It should be noted that the description of buildings in the International Style category also appears in the works of Luminița Machedon¹²⁴ These are characterized by severity, sobriety, and a functional aesthetic (summarized as “form follows function”), with an almost total absence of decorative elements, and the use of vertical accents overlaid by horizontals in band-like subassemblies.

Mihaela Criticos, in her volume *Ornament. Theme and Variations*, contrasts the International Style and Art Deco with regard to the treatment of ornament. Describing the evolution of Modernism in Romania, Criticos asserts that Modernism developed an **empiricist strand**—soft, moderate, cordial, characteristic of Arts and Crafts and the Art Deco movement, with a tendency toward modern decorative expression—and a **hard strand**—rational, austere, radical, characteristic of the International Style, marked by anti-decorativism¹²⁵. In the same volume, Criticos emphasizes the significant contribution of the International Style’s iconoclasm, which abolishes traditional ornament and, as a consequence, stimulates the exploration of new formal solutions in Art Deco. These solutions, unintentionally compensatory, employ form and material in a manner that confers an intrinsically decorative function. In this way, form and material “broadened the contemporary understanding of the notion of ornament and even contributed to the recovery of its original meaning.” As illustration, the author suggests that the immaculate parallelepiped or the transparent box, the precise cut-outs of openings, the silhouettes of suspended staircases (likely referring to service access), as well as cantilevered awnings and balconies, become “figures of a rhetoric that systematically eliminates any historical reminiscence”¹²⁶.

De Stijl accents are described and exemplified by Mihaela Criticos in *Art Deco or Well-Tempered Modernism*, and are recognizable in Jean Văleanu’s buildings through the treatment of the intrados of entrance canopies, which receive an ornamental articulation via stepped setbacks, recessed panels, and illuminated surfaces. According to Criticos, the influence is particularly evident in the special plastic role assigned to the canopies at the upper levels of the buildings, which both double and emphasize the contours, animating the composition through echoes of the

¹²⁴ Luminița Machedon, Florin Machedon, *op.cit.*, p. 163, Luminița Machedon, Ernie Scoffman, *op.cit.*, *loc.cit.*

¹²⁵ Mihaela Criticos, *Ornament. Temă și variațiuni*, Editura Simetria, Bucharest, 2005, p. 64.

¹²⁶ Mihaela Criticos, *op.cit.*, p. 127.

“deconstruction” practiced by the De Stijl movement, here transposed into a decorative register¹²⁷. The influence is also evident in the modernist design of the floors, which adopt an exuberant geometry reflecting the contributions of Cubism and De Stijl¹²⁸. This geometric play is also reflected, as in certain buildings in France and Germany, in the articulation of façades with irregularly patterned parapets, which confer a distinctive identity to the building at Aron Florian 4bis (see Figure 25).

The analysis of the use of material as ornament, of light as ornament, of the treatment of solid and void surfaces, and of subassemblies receiving accents that define the specificity of Art Deco façades was drawn from Mihaela Criticos’s research. Her work has been employed in the present study to identify a guiding thread that delineates Jean Văleanu’s stylistic signature. The categories outlined are summarized in the appendix to visually convey the architect’s preferences for certain portals, materials, geometric patterns in floors, interior doors, and forms (see appendix).

Gruparea imobilelor pe criterii stilistice.

Mature Art Deco. This stylistic option appears exclusively in medium-sized buildings. It is characterized by the use of unprofiled light-colored plaster and features distinctive elements such as multi-level corner windows, vertical slits marking the stairwell, and parapets with aerodynamic lines articulated by transverse-bar balustrades. Buildings in the mature Art Deco style are dated to the period 1932–1936, and only corner solutions aligned with the streetfront are known, typically with a height of ground floor plus three stories and a single access. Flooring is executed in dark-toned mosaic concrete, and the lines of the interior stair balustrades show De Stijl influences.

Art deco with Expressionist accents. One corner building following the curvature of the street from Văleanu’s early period was identified, located at Aron Florian 4bis (6). Its relatively typical Expressionist façade reveals explorations of irregular forms: the overall plan is polygonal, and the façade is dominated by rounded parapets that fold and bend. Recessed slits form niches within the interior wall, subordinating the play of light to emphasize volumes and voids.

¹²⁷ Mihaela Criticos, *Art Deco sau Modernismul bine temperat*, p. 207.

¹²⁸ Idem, *op.cit.*, pp. 177–178.

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Mature Art deco

22, 23. Chamfered corner, Caimatei 16

24. The staircase features a chamfered corner window extending over three levels, with vertical setbacks and parapets shaped as half-ellipses.

Dimitrie Onciul 29

24

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Expressionist accents

25. Aron Florian 4bis (today no. 6)

Streamline. Included in this category are the projects at Victor Babeş 1–5, as well as Calea Moşilor 86, featuring a convex façade and an overall sectoral plan (or wedge-shaped plan)¹²⁹. Streamline influence is evident in aerodynamic lines of ribbon windows, articulating façades.

Art Deco with Streamline accents. The numerous buildings executed in this style are emblematic of the architect's personal imprint. Located predominantly in the Armenesc–Evreiesc district, these are medium-sized buildings characterized by highly plastic façades, an interplay of straight and aerodynamic lines, and the use of quarter-cylinder junctions clad in marble or mosaic concrete, alongside other high-quality materials. Interiors are articulated with coves, slots, perforations, and ribbings. Entrances are distinguished by the juxtaposition of glazed surfaces—typically frosted glass—with decorative metalwork. The comb-like projections and the alternation of curved and rectilinear forms are hallmark compositional devices of Văleanu's style. His projects, situated at the intersection of Art Deco and Streamline, demonstrate both abundance of creative resources and confident handling of Deco vocabulary. A defining feature in Văleanu's Streamline-inflected works is transparency: the articulation of façade reflects the underlying internal structure, expressed externally through slots, skylights, bay windows, projections, setbacks, and oculus-type openings.

International style and functionalism. This applies to large-scale buildings, featuring articulated elevation planes, setbacks at upper floors, separate entrances for residents and service staff, elevators. Crisp lines and façades tend toward simplicity and sobriety. The stylistic language aligns with modernist tendencies—Art Deco, International Style, and Streamline. These choices do not stem from a client's taste, but are dictated by the constraints and possibilities inherent in the parcel's configuration and the existing built context. A complementarity is observable between Jean Văleanu's buildings and their neighboring structures, creating a dialogue, including mirrored arrangements. Most buildings adhere to the street alignment, while some follow the contours of the sidewalk or roadway, reflecting the architect's approach of integrating the built environment harmoniously within the preexisting urban fabric.

¹²⁹ The Romanian term of „felie de placinta overall plan” a fost preluat ca atare din Valentin Popescu, *Metaphors Shaping Modern Architecture in Interwar Romania: Mental models and architectural discourse*, Logos Universality Mentality Education Novelty Philosophy and Humanistic Sciences, 2022 și Luminița Machedon, Ernie Scoffman, *op.cit.*, Ileana Burnichioiu, „The historical and residential architecture under totalitarian regimes and after. The Romanian case”, în *Annales Universitatis Apulensis Series Historica*, tom1 .2017, pp. 13-44

26

27

Streamline

26, 27. Streamline,
Wedge shaped plan
Calea Moșilor 86

International style

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28. Take Ionescu 26/
Block Casata

29. Calea Plevnei 1

30. Călușei 20-22

31. Perspective towards
the Casata Building from
the Leonida building,
circa 1941

Take Ionescu 26

31

Accents and details. The buildings designed by Jean Văleanu, with variations on the Art Deco idiom, share a common denominator in their meticulous attention to detail. Although recurring elements can be observed—such as window typologies, solutions for façades or corners, materials employed for exterior and interior walls, or pavements—each building possesses a distinct identity. This identity emerges from the use of material as ornament, as well as from the articulation of space through solids and voids. The following analysis examines specific cases that exemplify the use of material as ornament (metal, marble, granite, travertine, translucent glass), light as ornament (both direct and indirect, natural and artificial), and the treatment of closed surfaces (walls, parapets, ceilings, floors) and open surfaces (windows, display cases, skylights, portals). It also considers the treatment of architectural subassemblies as volumetric-spatial elements (stairwells, projections, corners) and the motifs employed in diverse combinations—geometric-abstract patterns, sunburst motifs, stepped forms—all of which constitute stylistic traits of a defining decorative language.

Material as ornament. The Art Deco period was relatively unconstrained by financial limitations, which allowed the selection of precious, high-quality, and durable materials, resulting in decorative solutions both lasting and visually impactful. The expressive potential of materials—their textures, colors, patterns, reflections, brilliance, absorption or reflection of light, and transparency—are amplified both by the absence of conventional ornamentation and by their use in inventive combinations that mutually enhance one another. Finishing materials for large horizontal or vertical surfaces are particularly striking: exterior walls often employ *calcio vecchio* plaster with evident ornamental qualities, while interior walls are clad in contrasting marble or travertine, typically elevating the main entrances. Stone is often juxtaposed with mosaics or dark-hued terrazzo floors, occasionally arranged in monochrome or polychrome patterns. Glass, frequently treated through etching, sandblasting, or casting, is employed in conjunction with artificial interior lighting effects. However, the material that most distinctly defines the Art Deco style is metal. It is used inventively in railings, balconies, staircases, grilles, canopies, window and portal hardware, lighting fixtures, and, notably, handles. The application of metal details with established abstract-geometric motifs, along with the superimposition of horizontal, vertical, and undulating planes, transforms objects of purely functional utility into decorative elements in their own right.

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Material as ornament

Travertine and terrazo

32, 33. The interior walls juxtapose **travertine** and **mosaic concrete**, producing a striking monochrome contrast

Vasile Lascăr

Metal and glass

34

34. **Detail of the entrance portal**, featuring thin panes of transparent glass

Victor Babeş 5

35

35. **Detail of the window**, combining external decorative metalwork with frosted glass panes,

Caimatei 16

36

36. Details of indoor doors,

Maria Rosetti 36

Light as ornament. A defining innovation of Art Deco lies in the manipulation and capture of light within architectural volumes, as well as in the amplification of material qualities, achieved through the subordination of light and the modeling of luminous matter. In this way, Art Deco architects operate as “sculptors of light,” analogous to Baroque sculptors who treated water as a malleable medium in the design of fountains. Paraphrasing Mihaela Criticos, light acquires material presence and assumes an architectural role, interacting dynamically with other compositional elements.

The innovative use and control of light—whether direct or diffuse, natural or artificial—characteristic of Jean Văleanu, yet widely deployed across Art Deco practice, is evident in his interior schemes. Here, lighting transcends mere utilitarian function to become fully integrated into the architectural vocabulary. Light assumes an ornamental function, articulating planes, volumes, and the formal rhetoric of the design. Spaces are conceived to maximize natural illumination during the day, while simultaneously accommodating artificial lighting strategies that extend the expressive and functional capacities of the architecture after dark.

Artificial light is captured and articulated through panels, soffits, occasionally integrated luminous fixtures set into ceilings, as exemplified by the Teatrul Modern and certain residential buildings, such as the apartment block at Ion Brezoianu 51. Art Deco aesthetic subordinates illumination to overall compositional schemes. Natural light is transmitted either through clear or frosted glass, enhancing material qualities and emphasizing textures through subtle plays of light and shadow—for instance, the veining or granularity of natural stone and processed glass. Whether natural or artificial, light is incorporated scenographically, particularly in the modeling of stairwells, which are often accentuated by skylights or horizontal light slots, sometimes following aerodynamic lines, as in the Aron Florian 4bis building. Interposed obstacles selectively channel natural light, producing effects that shape both the spatial perception and the experiential qualities of the interior. The preciousness of materials—finely detailed mosaic concrete in black, white, and gold, brass and chrome-plated steel balustrades, granite and travertine cladding—are maximized and valorized through carefully orchestrated artificial lighting. Jean Văleanu employs these effects strategically to define spatial hierarchies and accentuate architectural elements. This approach is evident in the differentiation and zonation of

spaces in the buildings at Maria Rosetti 36 and Vasile Lascăr 23–25, where the portal and entrance staircases are illuminated either by natural light or indirect artificial lighting, in contrast to the stairwell proper, which receives direct illumination and is further articulated through flooring patterns and material detailing.

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Light as ornament

37. Interior wall sculpted with aerodynamic lines, direct natural light to create intricate patterns of shadow and illumination, Aron Florian 4bis

38. Natural light carefully orchestrated to serve the overall composition, accentuating volumetric relationships and the sculptural articulation of space, Vasile Lascăr 23-25

39. Natural light employed to articulate spatial zones, mirrors are strategically used to amplify and extend light throughout effects, Armenească 19

40. Coffers, neon tubing Vasile Lascăr 23-25

41. Natural and artificial light sculpt space, highlight materiality and serves zonification, Ferdinand 17

Treatment of surfaces: Closed and open planes. In Jean Văleanu’s Art Deco buildings, the treatment of closed surfaces—walls, ceilings, floors, parapets—and open elements—portals, windows, niches, slots, and skylights—creates façades that are both individually expressive and conceptually unified. Attention to detail is the guiding thread of his entire oeuvre. Even in smaller, simpler buildings on challenging plots, the careful modulation of solids and voids demonstrates a deliberate strategy to maximize the ornamental potential of form itself.

Exterior walls often follow a curved, typically aerodynamic line, though façades are articulated through concave and convex volumes, as seen at Victor Babeş 5. The aerodynamic motif extends to parapets and corner setbacks at Maria Rosetti 36 and creates horizontal accents at Calea Moşilor 86. Straight lines and vertical emphasis dominate larger-scale projects aligned with the International Style or hybrid approaches, such as Take Ionescu 26 (Blok Casata), Calea Plevnei 1 (Blok Lazăr), and collaborative works with Jean Monda (Take Ionescu 29, Eforie 6). Parapets and “comb”-type bay windows showcase the expressive potential of line, sometimes featuring double setbacks in both horizontal and vertical planes. Ceilings are treated with niches, soffits, and recesses, enhancing interior individuality while reflecting the exterior compositional symmetry. Quarter-cylinder moldings appear at portals (Ferdinand 17, Alexandru Donici 36) and on parapets at Maria Rosetti 36, emphasizing a meticulous orchestration of form across surfaces.

Treatment of Openings: The “Identity Card” of Small-Scale Buildings. Open spaces define the character of Văleanu’s smaller projects, encompassing a wide range of variations. Skylights trace straight lines or appear in hexagonal sections, while corner windows rise across three levels. Window types are highly diverse: portholes, horizontal slits, and ribbon windows typical of Modernism, all reflecting a deliberate avoidance of superfluous ornament. The arrangement of windows imparts transparency and visual honesty, directly expressing the floor plan and overall compositional logic of each building.

Entrances and Portals: Signatures of Identity. Văleanu’s portals evolve from austere, minimalist-geometric schemes to intricate compositions where textured glass is paired with finely crafted, elaborate metalwork. They define the identity of each building and assertively mark the façades. Often, they are echoed vertically in the elevation through a pediment or a

skylight over the stairwell. Notably, in Văleanu's work, decorative motifs are never repeated verbatim from one building to another, emphasizing the singularity of each project.

Decorative Motifs: Art Deco Signatures. Văleanu's buildings feature canonical Art Deco motifs, most notably the stepped forms. These appear either vertically, in the setbacks of upper floors (Take Ionescu 26, Alexandru Donici 36, Calea Moșilor 86, Calea Victoriei 101), or horizontally, in the retreat of bay windows and transitional interior spaces (Vasile Lascăr 23–25). The motif becomes both structural and ornamental, articulating volume while enhancing the overall compositional rhythm of the façade.

Geometric-Abstract Motifs. Geometric-abstract motifs recur throughout Văleanu's decorative metalwork on windows, skylights, and portals. They range from minimal expressions—seen in shopfronts and commercial portals (Calea Victoriei 101, Vasile Lascăr 23–25, Calea Plevnei 1)—to more complex and lavish compositions, as at Alexandru Donici 36, Armenească 19, and Victor Babeș 5. Specific motifs include the zig-zag at the portal on Strada Caimatei 16 and sunburst patterns in both metalwork and mozaic concrete at Ferdinand 17, as well as at Entrance B of the Calea Victoriei 101 apartment block.

Urban Planning Implications in Văleanu's Projects. The 1935 urban systematization plan introduced innovations that reshaped both the city's circulation arteries and the visual cohesion of buildings. As Octav Doicescu observed, *“any external plastic element creates the atmosphere of the city. As this atmosphere affects the people gathered within the settlement and determines a kind of destiny of coexistence, there must be responsibility and control. A house built [that] fails to meet even the minimum standards of aesthetic correctness (...) diminishes the spirituality of both the individual and the city.”* Văleanu's designs reflect these principles: strict adherence to street alignments, uniform building heights, and attention to comfort standards, quantified through air volume, consistent thermal and ventilation regimes, and cross-ventilation. His projects thus integrate urbanistic responsibility with architectural expression, ensuring that each building contributes to a coherent and humane urban fabric.

Urban Planning Compliance and Technological Adaptation in Văleanu's Projects. Jean Văleanu's adaptation to municipal urbanism regulations is exemplified by the iterative approvals for the building at **Calea Victoriei 101 (1936–1938)**. Initially planned as a ground

plus ten-story structure, successive revisions reduced it to eight stories, with alignment constraints shaping the final building footprint. This *plomb* building—as well as **Take Ionescu 29**, **Eforie 6**, and corner sites like **Thomas Masaryk** or **Armenească**—demonstrates strict compliance with height regulations and visual harmonization with adjacent structures.

Alignment adherence is evident along **Magheru–Bălcescu** and in large-scale apartment buildings such as **Eforie 6**, **Calea Plevnei 1**, **Vasile Lascăr 23–25**. Technological innovations and mandatory comfort standards (air quality, thermal regulation, daylight) are articulated in Văleanu’s designs. The **interior courtyard of Calea Victoriei 101** ensures uniform natural lighting for all apartments in the two wings. Ventilation shafts are systematically integrated on all floors in buildings constructed after 1935 (e.g., **Vasile Lascăr 23–25**, **Maria Rosetti 36**, **Calea Plevnei 1**), contrasting with early small-scale projects such as **Caimatei 16** and **Aron Florian 4bis**, where lack of such measures results in a persistently lower comfort standard.

Technological integration also encompasses **electric lighting, full-day thermal comfort, built-in heating appliances (radiators, convectors), and passenger elevators** in larger buildings. These features, often highlighted in contemporary apartment sale advertisements, underscore the strong appeal of Văleanu’s projects to middle-class residents and illustrate the architect’s capacity to reconcile urban regulations, technical innovation, and market demand.

Adaptation to Parcel Conditions. One of the clearest demonstrations of Jean Văleanu’s versatility and spatial intelligence lies in his treatment of irregular and constrained plots. His buildings optimize every square meter, responding to site geometry with inventive planimetric solutions.

For instance, the **Victor Babeş 1 and 5** buildings adopt a *pachebot*-style configuration. Each building maintains its individual form, yet together they create a coherent ensemble, framing the intervening structure while preserving a visual continuity (see Figure 42, research by the author). Corner plots are often resolved with **L-shaped plans**, as seen in **Thomas Masaryk 9** and **Armenească 19**, while parcels with wedge-shaped footprints, such as **Calea Moşilor 86**, are treated with a *pie-slice* plan.

Across these examples, Văleanu demonstrates a remarkable capacity to adapt the architectural program to pre-existing site conditions, turning potential constraints into opportunities for formal inventiveness and articulation of volumetric and compositional clarity.

The buildings on this narrow, elongated parcel exemplify Jean Văleanu’s mastery of site-specific design. The two structures at **Victor Babeș 1 and 5** are conceived as a coherent *pachebot* ensemble: each building maintains its distinct identity while the central intervening space is treated as a visual and functional connector, framing the ensemble with continuity. The parcel’s geometry—long, narrow, and bounded by two streets—dictated the linear arrangement, the placement of entrances, and the articulation of facades.

Văleanu exploited this constrained site to emphasize **corner accents, aerodynamic façades, and step-back volumes**, creating rhythm and hierarchy while ensuring light penetration and ventilation. The result is a sophisticated interplay of massing, circulation, and ornament, turning a challenging infill site into an opportunity for compositional elegance and urban dialogue.

Figure 42. Use of the Parcel between Victor Babeș and Dr. Frederic Joliot Curie

Figure 43. Building plan Armenească 19

Figure 44. Calea Moșilor 86

Conclusions on the Architectural Work of Jean Văleanu

The systematic inventory and thematic categorization of Jean Văleanu's built projects reveal a profound **receptivity to the nuances of Art Deco**, the style he consistently favored. His stylistic versatility is most evident in the numerous solutions devised for medium-sized apartment buildings, particularly in challenging parcels—such as **Calea Plevnei 1, Călușei 20–22, and Caimatei 16**—demonstrating a skillful adaptation to pre-existing urban contexts.

Certain buildings assert themselves as defining elements of their respective urban squares (**Maria Rosetti 36, Calea Moșilor 86**), while others establish a harmonious dialogue with surrounding structures. For instance, the two independent buildings at **Caimatei 14 and 16** maintain symmetry and functional connectivity, forming a **cour ouvert** despite the courtyard being visually and physically divided by a fence.

The richness of Văleanu's architectural vocabulary—expressed through **geometric motifs, compositional solutions, aerodynamic lines, and the alternation of solid and void, curved and straight elements**—imparts a distinctive “Văleanu signature” to his works. His inventive, confident approach, combined with a specialization in residential architecture, substantiates the characterization of Văleanu as an **Art Deco residential architect of the first rank**, whose reputation in Bucharest was such that the **Take Ionescu 26 building, constructed in 1937, was marketed as “Blok Văleanu”** to maintain premium value.

Overall, Văleanu's legacy illustrates **a masterful integration of style, functionality, and urban sensitivity**, confirming his position among the leading figures of the Romanian Art Deco movement.

CHAPTER 4. The artist Jean Văleanu

The architect **Jean Văleanu** is also recognized as a visual artist, working in **oil, acrylic, gouache, and pencil sketches**. His first public acknowledgment as an artist dates to **1936**, when the daily newspaper *Lupta* described him as “not only an accomplished architect but also an indisputable artist”¹³⁰. This suggests that, **at least within the Jewish community, the architect was already recognized as active in the visual arts**.

Jean Văleanu’s artistic trajectory is outlined by the art historian Vasile Florea in the *Encyclopedia of Contemporary Artists*. According to this source, his training began early, “in the home of Friedrich Storck and Cecilia Cuțescu-Stork, from whom he received his first lessons in the art of color”¹³¹. His work as a painter is believed to have developed alongside his architectural practice, both in Italy—likely during his studies—and later in Romania and France. From 1978 onward, his artistic production became his primary focus. Vasile Florea notes Văleanu’s participation in the largest official exhibition of painting and sculpture held at Sala Dalles after 23 August 1944, where he exhibited two works, including a portrait of the comedian Timică, which was acquired by the Bulandra Theatre¹³². The art historian notes a retrospective exhibition hosted in July 1999 at the Parisian studio of painter Gen Paul in Montmartre, corroborated by exhibition posters and digital reproductions of over twenty works included in the show (reproductions are provided in the appendix¹³³). The source notes that Văleanu began with landscape compositions executed on canvas, depicting the seashore at Costinești as well as the Bucharest Village Museum. These works are treated in a traditional execution style, yet exhibit a tendency toward flattening of form. Created “under the influence of the sun and marine atmosphere that had captivated numerous Romanian artists, the Dobrogea-period works reveal

¹³⁰ Adrian Vereă, „Cronica Teatrală. Teatru Moden: 9000 de franci recompensă de A. Laszlo”, in *Lupta*, year 15, no. 4558 dated 29.12.1936, p. 2

¹³¹ Vasile Florea, op.cit., loc.cit.

¹³² Representatives of the Bulandra Theatre have stated that they do not hold such a work, and his participation in exhibitions after 1944 is not confirmed by the works of Petre Oprea.

¹³³ Available at Flickr @mtowers2008, uploaded at 05.09.2009, link <https://www.flickr.com/photos/29253252@N07/> accesat la 02.06.2025

the temperament of a painter in love with color, applied boldly and with an intensity reminiscent of the Fauves”¹³⁴. Vasile Florea further describes Văleanu’s relaxed brushwork, the textured, almost kneaded appearance of the paint, and the seemingly casual treatment of forms, considering these qualities emblematic of the artist’s lyrical spirit, animated by poetic moods, and suggesting a certain distinction between the painterly and architectural facets of his creativity. The same chromatic range is applied in the landscape compositions of the Village Museum. It should be noted, however, that this so-called “Dobrogea period” likely also includes works from Balcic, where Jean Văleanu and his wife, Stela Văleanu, are documented in contemporary journals as frequent summer visitors, often guests at the villa of the Stork family. The only known detail regarding the Văleanu–Stork connection is the guidance and initiation in the plastic arts provided to Jean Văleanu by Cecilia Cuțescu-Stork, as cited in a single source.

The evolution of Jean Văleanu as a painter, as documented by the works presented in the 1999 retrospective exhibition in Paris, undergoes a relatively radical shift around 1985, marking his transition from figurative to abstract composition –

„he embraced abstract modes of expression, filling the surface of the canvas with images born of a prodigious imagination. On rectangular supports of canvas or cardboard, executed in oil, watercolor, or acrylic, the painter composes forms of sinuous lines—never straight—that often evoke the appearance of a biological tissue viewed under a microscope”¹³⁵.

The series of abstract works described by the historian is referred to in his brief biography as *Structures*. Vasile Florea notes that these compositions are constructed according to the principles of decorative abstraction, without recalling the oeuvre of any known painter. Nevertheless, the contemporary artistic activity of his wife, working in enamel and glass—as documented by Ionel Jianu in his 1985 treatise *Romanian Artists in the Diaspora*—attests to formal and chromatic affinities. Both Jean and Stela Văleanu employ a color palette aligned with *negrism*, a trend prevalent in Parisian society at the time, dominated by black, alongside green and magenta hues. Enamel works by Stela Văleanu from the 1970s are reproduced in the

¹³⁴ Vasile Florea, „Jean Văleanu” in *Enciclopedia Artiștilor Contemporani*, volumul 5, Arc 2000 publishing house, Bucharest, 2012, p. 197

¹³⁵ *Ibidem*, loc.cit.

annex¹³⁶. Stela Văleanu's artistic practice consistently complements that of Jean Văleanu. The same source highlights the symbiotic nature of their creative activity: she was frequently involved in her husband's architectural projects, producing enamel and glass panels for the buildings he designed. After relocating to Paris, Jean Văleanu continued his architectural career—automatically joining the Order of Architects—and notably designed the French Aviation Club on the Champs-Élysées. For this commission, Stela created a large-scale enamel panel, exemplifying their ongoing collaborative dialogue between architecture and the decorative arts.¹³⁷ Hence, it can be inferred that such collaborative associations between the two were a frequent practice.

In 1993, at the age of 99, Jean Văleanu was confined to bed following a car accident, a medical condition that imposed certain limitations on his working techniques. In this context, according to Vasile Florea, he suspended his easel work and restricted himself to drawing. The works included in the aforementioned exhibition feature a series of pencil nudes dated 1958, but the ones part of this third creative phase, had previously remained largely unknown¹³⁸.

The painterly activity of Jean Văleanu – an architect - is not in itself unprecedented, as most architects of his era produced hand-drawn studies, and several explored media such as gouache, oil, or watercolor – examples include George Simotta, George Mihai Cantacuzino, Marcel Iancu, and Virginia Andreescu Haret. What distinguishes Văleanu, however, is the fluidity with which he shifts the register of his plastic expression across periods. This activity, while distinct from his architectural practice, remains intertwined with it, reflecting the stages of his life: residence in Romania, artistic initiation under the guidance of Cecilia Cuțescu-Stork, summer sojourns along the Black Sea coast, relocation to France and engagement with local trends, as well as the physical constraints imposed by a car accident and advanced age. Văleanu's plastic work thus reveals a continual adaptation to circumstances and a personal artistic evolution – an artistic life with a life of its own. It demonstrates a persistent vein of creative activity sustained throughout his life, reflecting both necessity and vocation.

The works presented in the retrospective held at the Gen Paul Gallery in 1999 span the period 1957–1998 and encompass multiple genres: portraiture (a single surviving work identified

¹³⁶ Ionel Jianu, *Les artistes roumains en occident*, Editura: American Romanian Academy of Arts and Sciences, Bucharest, 1986, p. 179

¹³⁷ Vasile Florea, *op.cit, loc.cit.*

¹³⁸ Vasile Florea, *op.cit, loc.cit.*

digitally, as the piece acquired by the Bulandra Theatre could not be traced in this phase), two nudes (1958), still lifes (11 works from 1976–1993), landscapes (one from 1957, painted during his time in Costinești, two from the 1960s, and one from 1998), and non-figurative compositions, subdivided into the categories *Structures* (15 works, circa 1989–1998) and *Masks* (a self-designated series of 19 works, 1986–1998). These phases coexist, overlap, and succeed one another, characterized by freedom of line and compositional lyricism. Even in the earliest works included – the 1958 nudes – a confident hand is evident. The landscapes demonstrate a gradual evolution in spatial depth, observable when comparing the 1957 Costinești composition, which suggests a synthesis of the Black Sea coast and the Bucharest Village Museum, with the landscapes of 1969 and 1998.

Seriality becomes particularly evident in the still lifes, most notably in the recurring motif of four apples set against a clouded background, which, in my view, resonates with Surrealist echoes. This logic of repetition is further articulated in the recurring motif of the mask: a corpus of nineteen works that simultaneously recalls Francis Bacon’s serial explorations and the visual vocabulary of *negrism*, a current that marked French art in the second half of the twentieth century. The *Masks* evolve from flat, bidimensional, and deliberately simplified images toward compositions that suggest an interest in psychic processes, eventually adopting articulated, quasi-sculptural geometric volumes.

This serial impulse continues in the *Structures* series (as designated by Vasile Florea), where non-figuration gives way to an exploration of texture and decorative surface. As evidenced by the reproductions, these works are executed almost exclusively on cardboard, employing media that range from gouache to acrylic. The chromatic palettes of the *Masks* and *Structures* largely overlap; in some cases, individual *Masks* function as pendants to specific *Structures*, underscoring a sustained preoccupation with materiality.

Taken as a whole, the serial approach points to an interest in so-called “exotic” cultures, while simultaneously incorporating motifs evocative of Romanian folkloric masks. These visual correspondences find parallels in Stela Văleanu’s known enamel-on-copper works from 1973 and 1978—*Mon soleil* and *Le Couple*—reproduced in the study by Ionel Jianu, further reinforcing the dialogue between the two artists’ practices¹³⁹ and discussed in the page dedicated

¹³⁹ Ionel Jianu, op.cit., loc.cit.

to the artist by Vasile Florea in the aforementioned volume on contemporary Romanian artists, further reinforcing the dialogue between the two artists' practices¹⁴⁰.

Jean Văleanu's artistic activity, as prolific as his architectural practice, attests to his acute receptivity to artistic production in the West—particularly within the French context of the period—as well as to the symbiotic nature of his artistic practice and the continuity between his own visual language and that of his wife, the artist Stela Văleanu. The majority of the works presented in the retrospective exhibition were produced after the couple's relocation to Paris. With regard to this situation, the art historian Vasile Florea refers to instances of harassment by the Communist-regime secret service which, alongside the cultural policies of the regime, allegedly obstructed the removal of Văleanu's works from Romania. At present, the whereabouts of Jean Văleanu's artistic production executed in Romania remain unknown.

¹⁴⁰ Vasile Florea, „Stela Văleanu” in *Enciclopedia Artiștilor Contemporani*, volume 5, Arc 2000 Publishing house, Bucharest, 2012, p. 198

CONCLUSIONS

Jean Văleanu's Architectural and Artistic Contribution to the National Heritage.

In light of the foregoing analysis, the architectural activity of Jean Văleanu—of Jewish descent - and a major contributor to Bucharest's Art Deco built fabric—emerges as one of the most prolific episodes of the city's interwar and postwar architectural history. The impact of his oeuvre is particularly significant given the conditions of relatively broad creative freedom under which he operated. The urbanistic context of Bucharest's systematization generated large-scale demolitions, especially within residential districts, resulting in the creation of generous parcels. A number of these were capitalized upon by Jean Văleanu through forms of architectural entrepreneurship: he acquired multiple plots on which he designed and developed, under his own direction, over thirty identified buildings, out of an estimated total of approximately sixty projects attributed to his practice.

A discernible tendency emerges toward the adoption of a mature Art Deco vocabulary, with Streamline influences, favored in the construction of small-scale residential buildings in the Armenian–Jewish quarter. At the same time, Jean Văleanu engages the International Style with Deco inflections in larger residential developments along the Magheru–Bălcescu axis and within the Kogălniceanu district. This broad stylistic spectrum is further expanded by canonically Streamline buildings in the Cotroceni neighborhood which, alongside George Matei Cantacuzino's "ocean-liner" (paquebot) architecture—such as the Belona Hotel in Eforie Nord—may be situated within the formal explorations of Romanian architects whose contributions hold substantial significance for the development of local modern architecture.

His engagement as architect for purpose-built theaters and cinemas—such as the Modern Theatre and Cinema Excelsior—first and foremost signals his professional credibility and recognition as an established figure within local architectural circles during the early 1930s. Conversely, the insertion of cinemas at the ground floors of large-scale residential blocks

(notably Cinema Studio Constantin Notarra, presumed to have been located in the Magheru 29 block, and Cinema Eforie on the street of the same name) demonstrates his responsiveness to contemporary trends. These trends favored the abandonment of stand-alone cinema buildings in favor of their incorporation into mixed-use residential structures, thereby reinforcing their integration into the social fabric and everyday routines of the interwar bourgeois community.

His major contribution to the residential built fabric through *blokhaus*-type apartment buildings—his declared specialization, to adopt a term used in his personal file preserved in the archives of the Union of Architects of Romania—played a formative role in shaping the urban arteries that accommodated them. Through his design practice, much like that of his contemporaries, he actively contributed to the improvement of living standards within the society to which he belonged. This was achieved by incorporating the technological innovations of the period into his projects, with the explicit aim of providing maximum comfort accessible to the middle classes in the 1930s: electricity, heating systems operating continuously throughout the day and ensuring uniform thermal comfort across the entire building, optimal lighting conditions, reduced dwelling sizes coupled with functional zoning into day and night areas, and provisions for cross-ventilation.

At the same time, the relative absence of severe financial constraints allowed for the outfitting of these buildings—freed from overt, applied decorative elements—with high-quality materials of notable durability, which acquired an intrinsic decorative value beyond their utilitarian role. These included finely crafted metal balustrades (brass, wrought iron, chromed steel), applied or integrated lighting installations enabling the encapsulation of artificial light and the creation of lighting effects characteristic of Art Deco, high-grade processed glass, and natural stone used for pavements.

Last but not least, through the design of cinemas, theatres, and other leisure spaces articulated in an Art Deco idiom, Jean Văleanu introduced a form of accessible luxury into Bucharest's urban culture. Luminous foyers, the use of refined materials, segregated circulation and entrances, and individual cloakrooms assigned to each theatre box reflect design strategies already validated by the globally active Odeon theatre company. These architectural borrowings

translated the glamour popularized by Hollywood cinema into a spatial experience available to the urban middle classes, effectively democratizing luxury through architecture.

I would argue that by the late 1930s Jean Văleanu had effectively become a recognizable brand within the capital's real estate market. Contemporary advertisements identify residential developments as “Blok Văleanu,” a designation retained even in later private resale listings. This branding functioned as a form of symbolic capital and marketing upgrade, signaling construction quality, modern comfort, and stylistic prestige.

With regard to his artistic contribution, sustained at least from 1957 until the end of his life, Jean Văleanu emerges as a cultural mediator negotiating between the dominant artistic currents of postwar Paris, primitivist references drawn from Romanian folklore, and an engagement with so-called *art nègre*, most explicitly articulated in the *Masks* series. These concerns are particularly visible in the Parisian phase of his oeuvre—namely the *Masks* and *Structures* series, initiated in the 1980s—between which a sustained dialogue can be observed in terms of motifs, materials, techniques, and chromatic palettes.

Across both strands of Jean Văleanu's creative activity—architecture and visual art alike—the corpus of documented projects and works recovered through digital reproductions outlines a highly individualized, confident artistic profile that was not only coherent but also recognized, validated, and appreciated in its own time. Evidence of this contemporary recognition is provided by the aforementioned 1936 article published in the daily newspaper *Lupta*, which explicitly acknowledges Văleanu as “both an accomplished architect and an undisputed artist.”

Limitations of the Study. The research trajectory was constrained by the absence of references to Jean Văleanu in dictionaries dedicated to Romanian architects or modernist architects, leaving the available data minimal. Mentions extracted from contemporary press spanning 1929–1960 provide reliable indications regarding the buildings he designed, particularly the parcels he purchased and subsequently developed with residential or leisure properties. Certain buildings and projects attributed to Văleanu are explicitly cited in period newspapers—for example, the *Teatrul Vesel* and *Teatrul Modern*—while others appear in the classified sections as transactions involving land and real estate.

For a number of addresses that were entirely renovated, likely without adherence to the original plans, no period photographs were recovered, precluding definitive conclusions regarding the architect's stylistic choices. Furthermore, some buildings were destroyed during the Allied bombings of August 1944, and, to the best of my knowledge following research in photographic archives, visual documentation of these structures is either incomplete or entirely absent¹⁴¹, photographic documentation exists only in the form of ruins, within broader efforts to record the effects of bombings and earthquakes (as is the case for *Cinema Excelsior*, Strada Academiei). Furthermore, some identified addresses currently do not feature buildings characteristic of the period under study; understanding the development of construction in these instances would require exclusive consultation of the archives of the Bucharest City Hall (PMB). Additional difficulties arose in confirming the existence of buildings at addresses no longer recorded in the current street nomenclature, as the relevant PMB department had not, at the time of writing, provided information regarding historical postal numbering for these problematic cases.

Finally, not all sixty buildings presumed to have been designed by the architect are currently known; of these, approximately fifteen are thought to have been located in the Cotroceni district. This suggests the possibility that some buildings in the area were single- or two-family houses, commissioned privately, which would explain their absence from contemporary press announcements. Only one source mentions a project by Jean Văleanu in Timișul de Sus, Brașov County, which has not been identified to date (local authorities responded that no such building is known). Accordingly, all conclusions drawn from the thirty buildings that have been documented and analyzed may not fully represent the situation regarding the remaining thirty currently unknown buildings.

Jean Văleanu's personal and professional network remains only partially documented. His mentorship and friendship with the Stork family are attested in a single source, as is his participation in a major post-23 August 1944 exhibition, which remains unnamed and thus

¹⁴¹ *Biblioteca Academiei, Biblioteca Națională, Arhiva fotografică a Palatului Suțu, Biblioteca Centrală Universitară din Cluj-Napoca Academy Library, National Library, Photographic Archive of the Suțu Palace, Central University Library of Cluj-Napoca*

unidentified. Likewise, his architectural projects in Paris following emigration are largely unknown, with the exception of the French Aviation Club on the Champs-Élysées, and his early artistic works created during his time in Romania and Italy remain undocumented. Additionally, a request for access to his file at the National Council of State Security Archives has not yet been granted. Access to this dossier could potentially clarify the network of intellectual and artistic contacts surrounding him, as well as the individuals who facilitated his emigration and rapid incorporation into the French Order of Architects following his settlement in Paris.

Research conducted in the archives of the Kandinsky Library at the Musée Georges Pompidou revealed only a single handwritten letter sent by the architect's wife to the influential Parisian gallerist Iris Clert, which attests to a professional relationship between the Văleanu couple and Clert. In contrast to his wife's documented exhibition activity, Jean Văleanu's participation in international visual art exhibitions remains unknown. However, the issuance of his passport in 1960 provides a strong indication that he may have taken part in such events.

Recommendations for the Preservation of His Legacy In light of the evidence presented, Jean Văleanu emerges as a significant figure who should be included among the roster of Bucharest Art Deco architects active in the 1930s and 1940s, particularly those specializing in residential buildings. His contributions played a decisive role in shaping the capital's urban image, notably through Art Deco apartment blocks and projects reflecting the International Style. Văleanu's stylistic choices are vibrant and strongly individualized, revealing a personal aesthetic in residential architecture that both distinguishes the building itself and subtly reflects the identity of its client—different floors often feature distinct layouts, and apartments vary considerably in conceptual design. These decisions appear to have been informed primarily by his personal taste, while also responding to regulatory limitations imposed by the parcels he developed, in dialogue with contemporary urban planning regulations and the technological advancements integrated into Deco architecture.

Forgotten Legacy – Recovering Memory. This study would be incomplete without at least a speculative engagement with the question of why the architect Jean Văleanu has largely been relegated to the shadows—intentionally or otherwise—in the historiography of Art Deco architecture and of Bucharest during the period under analysis.

One potential factor behind the relative neglect of his contributions lies in his choice to pursue theoretical training at the University of Milan, specifically at the Politecnico di Milano. Observations suggest that the architects most prominently represented in the literature are those who studied at the Bucharest School of Architecture and, subsequently, held academic positions within its faculty. Another segment of better-documented architects tends to be those trained in the Beaux-Arts tradition.

A second factor is that Jean Văleanu did not belong to the major architectural offices formed around the prominent figures of the time, such as Duiliu Marcu. These professional circles were instrumental in promoting the visibility of certain architects, including George Matei Cantacuzino and Alexandru Zamfirescu (Zamphiropol).

Thirdly, Văleanu's Jewish origin was a significant factor that exposed him to ethnic discrimination and the implementation of fascist repressive measures targeting the Jewish community. The antisemitic currents of the era—extending beyond the period of the Legionary dictatorship and persisting throughout the twentieth century—likely contributed to Văleanu's exclusion from the ranks of architects who received high-profile civil commissions. An implicit consequence of this marginalization was the orientation of his practice toward private initiatives: residential buildings and leisure spaces, which historically have attracted less attention in the specialized literature than public or office buildings (for example, the ARO building).

Moreover, his membership in the Jewish minority shaped his professional and commercial networks, as evidenced by the concentration of his projects in the Armenesc-Evreiesc neighborhood and the predominance of transactions with other Jewish clients—such as apartment sales, collaborations with Jewish engineers like K. Davidovici, or joint projects with architect Jean Monda. Consequently, Jean Văleanu's architectural contributions were marginalized and overlooked in architectural historiography due to a dual process: the limited coverage in the contemporary press (outside Jewish newspapers) and systematic antisemitism.

Additionally, Văleanu's decision to emigrate permanently in 1960, and thus to sever official and irrevocable ties with the Communist regime of the Romanian People's Republic, generally resulted in the exclusion of such individuals from official historiography. For instance, Jean Văleanu contributed to the *Manualul Arhitectului* (Architect's Handbook) published

by Editura Tehnică in 1954—a work for which no copies are currently available in any of the specialized library collections surveyed to date¹⁴². Consequently, it cannot be excluded that, following his emigration, Jean Văleanu became a professionally “unmentionable” figure for both the architectural guild and subsequent historians—an outcome rendered ironically, or perhaps fatefully, in light of the fact that he had previously been decorated by the Romanian Communist Party for his outstanding contributions to the country’s postwar reconstruction. One likely consequence of this marginalization was the absence of commemorative plaques bearing his name from the Union of Architects during the Communist period—a distinction, for example, not denied to prolific and highly significant contemporaries such as George Matei Cantacuzino and Toma Socolescu, son of Toma T. Socolescu.

Văleanu’s erasure is further evidenced by the treatment of collaborative projects with Jean Monda, another Jewish architect educated at Politecnico Milano. While contemporary press from 1947–1948 explicitly identifies these works as joint endeavors, later accounts attribute them solely to Monda, thereby obscuring Văleanu’s authorship.

At this stage of research, it remains unknown whether Văleanu ever returned to Romania, as surviving contacts in his familial and professional circles provide only confirmation of post-emigration interactions, without substantive biographical or documentary support.

Another factor contributing to his historical invisibility is his prior association with Zionist and liberal milieus, which were disfavored under the authoritarian regime established after 1948. According to Vasile Florea, Văleanu was subjected to subtle forms of repression—so-called “harassment”—by the Securitate, although these measures remain insufficiently documented pending further investigation in the archives of the National Council for the Study of the Securitate Archives (CNSAS).

Finally, Văleanu’s marginalization can also be explained by the highly competitive environment of his era. Despite producing a substantial and coherent architectural oeuvre, he did

¹⁴² Academy Library, National Library of Romania, “Ion Mincu” University of Architecture and Urbanism Library, History Faculties Libraries of the University of Bucharest (UNIBUC) and Babeş-Bolyai University (UBB), Technical University of Cluj-Napoca Library, Central University Library of Cluj-Napoca

not introduce innovations comparable to contemporaries such as Marcel Herman Iancu, George Matei Cantacuzino, Horia Creangă, or Octav Doicescu. Other prominent figures who successfully navigated both Modernist and Neo-Romanian currents—Duiliu Marcu, Octav Doicescu, George Simotta—have received far greater attention in the literature, leaving Văleanu comparatively underrepresented in historiographical accounts of interwar and postwar Romanian architecture.

Jean Văleanu's relative invisibility can also be attributed to his lack of participation in professional committees, such as those dedicated to urbanism or monuments. Additional factors arise from the fact that architects more widely recognized in the literature were often authors of theoretical works or reflective accounts of their own practice—for instance, G. M. Cantacuzino published *Arcade și firide* and contributed to the founding of the journal *Simetria*, Duiliu Marcu authored theoretical treatises, and *Spre o arhitectură modernă* was a co-authored manifesto by Marcel Iancu, Horia Creangă, and Octav Doicescu. Unlike these contemporaries, Văleanu did not publish texts or articles, and therefore did not cultivate a presence in the theoretical discourse that structured the reception of modernist and Art Deco currents in Romania.

For these presumable reasons, I argue that the literature has largely overlooked his contributions to Bucharest's built heritage. This oversight has produced a noticeable gap in specialized bibliographies, with broader implications for the historical memory of his work and its significance for Romania's national culture and architectural patrimony.

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For these presumable reasons, I argue that the literature has largely overlooked his contributions to Bucharest's built heritage. This oversight has produced a noticeable gap in specialized bibliographies, with broader implications for the historical memory of his work and its significance for Romania's national culture and architectural patrimony.

Conclusions - Implicațiile studiului pentru istoria arhitecturală și culturală.

This study introduces new insights regarding the artistic and architectural activity of Jean Văleanu, innovations that establish him as one of the relevant Art Deco architects of the 1930–1948 period. It allows for the discernment of the evolution of his stylistic choices and the impact of his projects on the shaping of Bucharest’s built heritage.

The methodology employed enabled the exploitation of previously unexamined primary sources, the correlation of theoretical works with discoveries and building attributions, and the bringing to light of a significant portion of the architect’s projects, facilitating his repositioning within the community of architects who primarily practiced Art Deco and specialized in residential *blokhaus* buildings.

His architectural work is complemented by a parallel artistic practice, with identified works exhibited at the 1999 retrospective at Galerie Gen Paul in Paris. This study highlights the complementary elements between Jean Văleanu’s plastic work and that of his wife, Stela Văleanu. I argue that the evolution of themes, motifs, and color palettes characterizing both artists occurred simultaneously, reflecting personal experiences and their exposure to contemporary artistic currents in Paris.

From this perspective, Jean Văleanu emerges as a figure of relevance within the Bucharest architectural community during the Art Deco period, particularly amidst the major political and social transformations under authoritarian regimes. I also consider him a significant visual artist, a Romanian in the diaspora whose practice retains characteristics typical of Romanian painters from the 1930–1940s—predilection for certain themes, media, and color palettes, a flattened treatment of landscapes—while assimilating new trends specific to his time and place, including Surrealist influences, echoes of Francis Bacon, Western concerns with exotic subjects, and the inclusion of chromatic and thematic elements drawn from negrism, folklore, and possibly mysticism, manifested in abstract, non-figurative compositions that lean toward decorativism.

Therefore, I contend that further study of Jean Văleanu’s work as both architect and artist—examining not only the knowledge gap regarding his Bucharest period but also his

formative years in Milan and later in Paris—can contribute to a more complete understanding of the Romanian cultural landscape in the period immediately preceding Carol II's dictatorship and extending to the establishment of the Communist regime, particularly by documenting a practice that, after 1945, remained outside the realm of Socialist Realism.

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APPENDIX

Figure 45. Photograph of the architect, source: Architects' Association File no. 2335, holdings of the Romanian National Archives

REGATUL ROMANIEI
PRIMARIA ORAȘULUI BUCUREȘTI
 PLASA BĂNEASA, JUDEȚUL ILFOV
OFICIUL STĂRII CIVILE
EXTRACT
 Din registrul actelor de NAȘTERE pe Anul 1904

No. 7053

Act de naștere a copilului **Jean**
 de sex **masculin**, născut **la casa** n. e. **cazului**
 la ora **12:00** **pe** meridian, în orașul București, în
 casa **părinților săi** din strada **Bella** No. **5**
 pe ul. **Str. Mito Vălcănuș** de anul **1904**, de profesie **conșilier**
 și al. **Doi Julia născ. Schopf** de anul **1882**, de profesie **fără**
 după declararea făcută de către **tatăl**
 care ne-a prezentat copilul

Martori au fost:
 D. **M. Sobet** de anul **1893**, de profesie **student**
 din strada **Nantukose** No. **3**
 D. **Ionuț Vasile** de anul **1892**, de profesie **angajat**
 din strada **Vasgarian** No. **15**
 care au subscris acest act, după ce s-a avut împreună cu Noi și cu declarantul
 Comitetul după lege de Noi **Simionu M. Ionescu, localnic**
 al Căminului București și alifer al străii locale.

DECLARANT: **M. Vălcănuș**
 Martori: **M. Sobet**
T. Vasile
 OFICER AL STĂRII CIVILE: **D. M. Ionescu**

Pentru conformitatea cu realitatea **M. Simionu**
 ieri la ora **12:00** ale lunii **Octombrie** anul **1904** a fost
 deosebit în **act**

OFICER AL STĂRII CIVILE:
 Director.

No. **34888**

14

Figure 46. Architect's birth certificate, source: architect's file from the holdings of the Romanian Union of Architects

DATE PERSONALE:

1. Numele **VĂLEANU JEAN**
2. Prenumele **JEAN**
3. Data și locul nașterii **București 5 Noembrie 1904**
4. Școala absolvită și data diplomei **Școala Superioară de Arhitectură din Milano (Italia) August 1929 echivalată în București în Februarie 1930**
5. Specialitatea *) **arhitectura de locuințe**
6. Activitatea profesională:

a) Lucrări proiectate, arătându-se dacă acestea au fost executate sau nu (se va indica data de proiectare și execuție), participarea la concursuri **)

- Cinema EXCELSIOR St. Academiei 1944**
- Cinema Magheru Bul. Șt. Magheru 29 1947**
- Teatrul Studio de Film C. Notara St. Săuculea 1936**
- Imobil Cămin Plevnei 1 (60 apart.) 1936**
- | | | |
|----|----------------------------------|------|
| 1. | St. Maria Rosetti 36 (30 apart.) | 1935 |
| " | St. Sf. Elefterie 18 (10 apart.) | 1935 |
| " | Bul. Magheru 26 (55 apart.) | 1937 |
| " | St. V. Lascau 23 (60 apart.) | 1937 |
| " | Calea Victoriei 101 (100 apart.) | 1938 |
| " | Bul. Magheru 29 (40 apart.) | 1946 |
| " | St. Brezoianu 57 (75 apart.) | 1947 |
| " | St. Argentina 33 | 1940 |
| " | Piața Coșbucianu 5 | 1935 |
| " | St. Donici 36 | 1937 |

Circa alte 60 imobile în București cu 2-30 apartamente în diferite străzi.

*) Se va completa în cazul când solicitantul a făcut studii de specialitate sau când — printr-o practică îndelungată s'a specializat într'un anumit domeniu ca: arhitectură industrială, agricolă, de locuințe, construcții sportive, decorație interioară, etc.

Figure 47. Personal data of the architect, source: Architect's File, holdings of the Romanian Union of Architects

Figure 48. Photo from Bucharest, probably dated 1935-1936, address Maria Rosetti nb. 36, source: armyuser.blogspot.com

APARTAMENTE, PRAVALII ȘI GARSONIERE
DE VÂNZARE

CASA BLOC „ITALIANA”
STR. VĂSILE LĂSCĂR 23 COLT ITALIANA

CASA BLOC Bd. TAKE IONESCU
COLT CU STR. ATHENA 23

Construită de arhitectul **JEAN VALEANU**

Predarea Octombrie 1937

INFORMAȚII

ARCHITECT
JEAN VĂLEANU

Str. Maria Rosetti 36
Tel. 2.16.41 — București

ȘI

AGENȚIA MONDIALĂ

Str. Brezoianu 17
Tel. 3.08.06 — București

16

Figure 49. Poster advertising the buildings designed and constructed by Jean Văleanu, 1937

Figure 50. Poster advertising the buildings designed and constructed by Jean Văleanu, 1936

Figure 51. Poster advertising the buildings designed and constructed by Jean Văleanu, 1945

Figure 52. Poster advertising the buildings designed and constructed by Jean Văleanu, 1936

Figure 54 – Poster advertising the buildings designed and constructed by Jean Văleanu in a chronological order

Nr. Crt.	Year	Adress	Style	Quarter
1	1932	Caimatei, 16	Mature Art deco	Armenesc-Evreiesc
2	1933	Ferdinand, 17	Art deco – streamline influence	Armenesc-Evreiesc
3	1934	Elisabeta, 5 <i>(Interior design of the Vesel Theatre, Eforia Spitalelor Palace)</i>		Centru
4	1934	Aron Florian, 4bis	Art deco - Expressionism	Armenesc-Evreiesc
5	1934	Calea Moșilor, 86	Streamlined art deco	Armenesc-Evreiesc
6	1934	Dimitrie Onciul, 29	Mature Art deco	Armenesc-Evreiesc
7	1935	Sfântul Elefterie, 18		Cotroceni
8	1935	Armenească, 19	Art deco – streamline influence	Armenesc-Evreiesc
9	1935	Calea Plevnei, 1	Functionalism	Izvor-Kogălniceanu
10	1935	Maria Rosseti, 36	Art deco – streamline	Armenesc-Evreiesc

			influence	
11	1935	Piața Kogălniceanu, 5	Mature Art deco	Izvor-Kogălniceanu
12	1935	Piața Kogălniceanu, 7-8	Mature Art deco	Izvor-Kogălniceanu
13	1936	Călușei, 20-22	Art deco – Functionalism influence	Armenesc-Evreiesc
14	1936	Lucaci, 29 (<i>Matei Basarab 27</i>)	Mature Art deco	Armenesc-Evreiesc
15	1936	Constantin Mille, 14 (<i>Teatru Modern</i>)	Mature Art deco	Center
16	1937	Alexandru Donici, 36	Art deco – streamline influence	Armenesc-Evreiesc
17	1937	Take Ionescu, 26 (<i>Casata</i>)	Functionalism influence	Magheru-Bălcescu
18	1937	Vasile Lascăr, 23-25	Art deco – streamline influence	Armenesc-Evreiesc
19	1938	Victor Babeș, 1	Streamlined art deco	Cotroceni
20	1938	Victor Babeș, 5	Streamlined art deco	Cotroceni

21	1938	Calea Victoriei, 101	Functionalism – accents of art deco	Centru
22	1939	Thomas Masaryk, 9	Art deco – streamline influence	Armenesc-Evreiesc
23	1940	Argentina, 40	Art deco – streamline influence	Dorobanți
24	1944	Academiei, 28 (<i>Cinema Excelsior</i>)		Centru
25	1945	Eforie, 6 (<i>collaboration with J. Monda</i>)	Art deco – Functionalism influence	Centru
26	1945	Cinema Eforie, 6 (<i>collaboration with J. Monda</i>)	Art deco – Functionalism influence	Centru
27	1947	Ion Brezoianu, 51	Funcționalism – Art deco accents	Cișmigiu
28	1947	Take Ionescu, 29 (<i>collaboration with J. Monda</i>)	Art deco – Functionalism influence	Magheru-Bălcescu

29	1947	Take Ionescu, 29 (<i>Film studio Constantin Notarra</i>)	Art deco – Functionalism influence	Magheru-Bălcescu
----	------	--	------------------------------------	------------------

L'ATELIER GEN PAUL
présente

JEAN VALEANU

Peintures anciennes
et
récentes

Vernissage :
le vendredi 2 juillet 1999 de 19 h à 22 h

Exposition :
du 3 au 23 juillet 1999 de 15 h à 19 h

Atelier Gen Paul - 2, avenue Junot - 75018 Paris
M° Lamarck Caulaincourt - ☎ 01.42.64.14.40

"Gen Paul (1895-1975), peintre, dessinateur, graveur est né rue Lepic à Paris, Montmartre. Sa peinture magistrale a depuis longtemps franchi les frontières. Elle est porteuse d'un grand impact spirituel..."

L'immense curiosité de l'artiste habité de musique et d'élévation spirituelle a permis à de grandes œuvres picturales de se faire jour, œuvres qui viennent du tréfonds de l'être et dans lesquelles par conséquent chacun peut retrouver le poids de son humanité."

Gabrielle Gen Paul

Jean Valeanu architecte, est né le 5 novembre 1904 à Bucarest où il exerça une activité très intense tant dans le bâtiment que dans la peinture.

Il s'est installé à Paris en 1960 avec son épouse Stella Valeanu, peintre émailleur. Il a été reçu, la même année, par l'Ordre des Architectes Français.

Il réalisa de nombreux bâtiments à Paris et ses alentours, sans délaissier pour autant la peinture à laquelle il se consacre maintenant pleinement.

Artistic activity

Jean Văleanu, *Peintures anciennes et récentes*, retrospective exhibition, 1999, Galerie Gen Paul, Paris.

54, 55, 56. Poster of the exhibit

57. Photo documenting the exhibit

54

56

55

57

58. Photo during the exhibit of artists Jean Văleanu and Stella Văleanu, 1999

59. Works dated 1993-1996

58

59

60

61

Nudes

60, 61. Nudes, 1958

62

Landscapes

62. Landscape Costinești – 1957

63. Landscape – 1969

63

64. Landscape – 1969

65. Landscape – 1998

64

Still life

65

66. Still life – 1976

66

67

67. Still life – 1979

68. Still life – 1989

69. Still life – 1981

68

69

70. Still life – 1979

71. Still life - 1993

70

71

72. Still life – 1989

73. Still life – nedatăă

72

73

74. Still life– 1998 or 1996

74

76,76. Still life – not dated

75

76

Masks

77, 78. Mask – 1986

79,80. Masks– 1986

77

78

79

80

81

82

81. Mask – 1987

82. Mask - 1988

83

84

83, 84. Mask - 1989

85

86

85. Mask – 1989

86. Mask - 1990

87

88

87. Mask – 1993

88. Mask - 1994

89

90

89, 90. Masks – 1995

91. Mask – 1995

91

92

92. Mask - 1998

93

94

95

93,94,95. Masks – not dated

Structures

96

96. Structures – 1989

97

97. Structures - 1992

98

98. Structures – 1993

99

99. Structures – 1994

100

100. Structures – 1996

101. Structures - 1996

101

102

103

102,103. Structures - 1998

104

105

104, 105. Structures - 1998

106

107

108

109

106, 107. Structures - 1998

108. Structures, 1999

109. Structures – not dated

110

110, 111. Structures – not dated

111

Known works by Stella Văleanu

112. Mon soleil – 1973, email on copper

113. Le couple – 1978, email on copper

112

113

Appendix - portals

114

115

116

117

118

119

Access portals – main facade

114. Calea Victoriei 101

115. Victor Babeş 5

116. Argentina 33

117. Bulevardul General

Magheru/Take Ionescu 29

118. Ferdinand 17

119. Armenească 19

Anexă - Pavements

120

121

122

123

124

125

Pavements

120. Aron Florian 4bis

121. Ferdinand 17

122. Alexandru Donici 36

123. Calea Victoriei 101 –
outside passage

124. Maria Rosetti 36

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Figure 150. Theatre Modern (today The Little theater), circa 1938

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Figure 152. The building at 86 Calea Plevnei, at the intersection with Radu Calomfirescu, 1960

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Figure 163. Casata building after the earthquake 1977.

■ Foto 5. Blocul Casata, 4 martie 1977

■ Photo 5. Casata Apartment Block, March 4, 1977

Figure 164. Building from Take Ionescu 29, collaboration with Jean Monda, photo dated 1961

Figure 165. Building from Calea Plevnei 1, view from the Bridge Izvor, dated 1939

Figure 166. View from the balcony of the Lazar block, Calea Plevnei 1, archive of Agrepres

Nr. Crt	Source of photos
1-7	Own research
8	Facebook page "Bucureștii vechi și noi", available at https://www.facebook.com/profile/100064687837133/ , dated 12.10.2021
9	Own research
10	Rendering available at https://www.behance.net/gallery/95092229/Jean-Valeanu-1938-Boat-house# , on the account @Nidrender Studio, data postării 09.04.2020
11	Rendering available at https://www.behance.net/gallery/95092229/Jean-Valeanu-1938-Boat-house# , account @Nidrender Studio, data postării 09.04.2020
12-15	Own research
16	Project Imagist "Am bulina mea", source https://www.imagist.ro/calea-plevnei-1/
17	Own research
18	Blog-ul "Armyuser", postarea https://armyuser.blogspot.com/2011/03/casa-bloc.html , dated 26.03.2011
19	Ion Diamandi, article "Un bloc modernist pe bulevardul General Magheru caracteristic perioadei interbelice", on the online newspaper Life and style, dated 16.08.2022, available at https://lifeandstyle.ro/index.php/2022/08/16/un-bloc-modernist-pe-bulevardul-magheru-caracteristic-perioadei-interbelice/

20	Facebook page "Cristi Radu", available at https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=10228442782953804&set=a.10212772175838420 , dated 26.08.2022
21-27	Own research
28	Magazine Arhitectura, nr. 4 dated 1975, page 1
29	Project Imagist "Am bulina mea", source https://www.imagist.ro/calea-plevnei-1/
30	Own research
31	Blog "Bucureștii vechi și noi", available at https://bucurestiiivechisinoi.ro/ , dated 30.01.2019
32-44	Own research
45	File no. 2335, Architects' Corps Fund, Romanian National Archives
46-47	Architect's dossier, found at the Union for Romanian Architects
48	Blog-ul "Armyuser", postarea https://armyuser.blogspot.com/2011/03/casa-bloc.html , data 26.03.2011
	Newspaper Adevărul, nr. 16383 dated 30.06.1937, page 2

49	
50	Newspaper Adevărul, nr. 15937 dated 03.01.1937, page 2
51	Universul - Capitala, august 1945, Year 62, nr. 193 dated 26.08.1945, page 2
52	Capitala, iulie-septembrie 1936, Year 1, nr. 134 dated 19.07.1936, page 4
53	Own research
54-111	Flickr account @mtowers2008, dated 05.09.2009, available at https://www.flickr.com/photos/29253252@N07/3889547465
112-113	Ionel Jianu, <i>Les artistes Roumains en Occident</i> , editura American Romanian Academy of Arts Sciences, 1986, page 179
114- 149	Own research
150	National Library of Romania, Special Collections, Inv. No. 101651_01
151	Blog "Bucureștii vechi și noi", available at https://bucurestiivechisinoi.ro/ , dated 30.01.2019
152	Bucharest Municipality Museum, Photography Archive, Inv. No. 8916

153	Blog "Bucureștii vechi și noi", available at https://bucurestiivechisinoi.ro/ , dated 30.01.2019
154	Vlad Eftenie, photo posted at https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=623439804369560&set=a.502840606429481
155	Bucharest Municipality Museum, Photography Archive, Inv. No. 33082-171
156	Bucharest City Hall Archive, Administrative Records Service, P.M.B. I Galben, File 172/1934
157	Bucharest Municipality Museum, Photography Archive, Inv. No. 10353
158	Bucharest Municipality Museum, Photography Archive, Inv. No. 104786
159	Bucharest Municipality Museum, Photography Archive, Inv. No. 47285
160	Blog "Armyuser", available at https://armyuser.blogspot.com/2011/03/casa-bloc.html , dated 26.03.2011
161	Blog "Bucureștii vechi și noi", available at https://bucurestiivechisinoi.ro/ , dated 11.01.2019
162	Blog "Bucureștii vechi și noi", available at https://bucurestiivechisinoi.ro/ , dated 23.01.2019

163	Magazine Transsylvania Nostra, nr,.4 dated 01.11.2014
164	Blog "Bucureștii vechi și noi", available at https://bucurestivechisinoi.ro/ , dated 23.01.2019
165	Blog "Armyuser", available at https://armyuser.blogspot.com/2011/03/casa-bloc.html , dated 26.03.2011
166	Blog "Bucureștii vechi și noi", available at https://bucurestivechisinoi.ro/ , from the Agerpress archive
167	File no. 2335, Architects' Corps Fund, Romanian National Archives

ACTIVITATEA ARHITECTURALĂ

JEAN VĂLEANU

1929: ABSOLVIREA INSTITUTULUI POLITECNIC MILANO
1930: ECHIVALAREA DIPLOMEI DE ABSOLVIRE
1931: INCLUDEREA SA ÎN CORPUL ARHITECȚILOR ROMĂNI

1932

strada Caimatei 16

1933

strada Ferdinand 17

1935

Planul de sistematizare

1934

Aron Florian 4
Calea Moșilor 86
Dimitrie Onciul 29

1935

Armenească 19, Calea Plevnei 1, Maria Rosseti 36, Pța Kogălniceanu 5, Piața Kogălniceanu 7-8

1936

strada Călușei 20-22
Teatrul Modern

1937

strada Al. Donici 36
Take Ionescu 26
Vasile Lascăr 23-25

1938

strada Victor Babeș 1 și 5
Calea Victoriei 101

1939

strada
Argentina 33
strada
Eforie 6/cu J. Monda

strada Th. Masaryk 9

1945

1940

1947

strada I. Brezoianu 51,
Magheru 29/cu J. Monda

1948

diriginte de șantier în MIM
emigrează în Franța

suspendarea dreptului de
liberă practică

1960

1951

